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Intelligent digital tools for screening of brain connectivity and dementia risk estimation in people affected by mild cognitive impairment

Deliverable 7.2

DISsemination and COmmunication Plan (DISCO Plan)

Version 1

WP7 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
H2020	Horizon 2020
WP	Work Package
WHO	World Health Organization
AI	Artificial Intelligence
MCI	Mild Cognitive Impairment
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
PESTEL	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, Legal
DISCO	DISsemination and COmmunication
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
SOTAC	Situation analysis, Objectives, Strategy, Tactic&Action and Control
SMCR	Sender, Message, Channel and Receiver
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

Partner short names

OUS	Oslo University Hospital
accelCH	accelopment Schweiz AG
AE	Alzheimer Europe
Brainsymph	BrainSymph AS
DNV	Det Norske Veritas
HUH	Helsinki University Hospital
IRCCS	Scientific Institute for Research, Hospitalization and Healthcare, San Raffaele Roma
Lurtis	Lurtis Rules S.L
UCM	Complutense University of Madrid
UCSC	Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore

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Executive Summary

Dissemination and communication are a core part of the AI-Mind project to ensure that project activities, resources and results are communicated and shared with the relevant stakeholders in a clear, consistent and effective manner. The presented DISsemination and COMMunication (DISCO) Plan introduces the AI-Mind project with its communication and dissemination strategies to achieve the greatest possible visibility, accessibility and promotion of the project and its results during the grant period. Broken down **into the seven key sections shown below**, the DISCO Plan provides a reference framework for AI-Mind to implement and evaluate dissemination and communication activities.

Background and Situation Analysis

As part of Task 7.1 defined in the grant agreement, to ensure maximum impact of the project results, accelCH will set up a target group-oriented open science dissemination and communication strategy with input from all partners. To ensure the DISCO Plan is in line with the project aims, the situation analysis, including SWOT and PESTEL analysis and benchmarking to other relevant initiatives, was performed to help AI-Mind better understand the needs of both the project and various groups.

Strategies

The AI-Mind DISCO strategy is based on four phases and combines two key elements: communication strategy and dissemination strategy. Through stakeholder analysis, including mapping them on the interest/impact matrix, AI-Mind is better able to tailor its key messages and define adequate measures to reach each target group in the most effective manner.

Channels and Tools

To guarantee the widest possible outreach, AI-Mind will employ a cross-channel and multimedia approach in its communication and dissemination activities. AI-Mind will use different channels, depending on the target audience, to convey its key messages, including in-person meetings, scientific publications, the project website and explanatory videos.

Implementation Pathway

Following the AI-Mind lifecycle of 60 months and reporting periods, the DISCO strategies will be rolled out in four phases. Both, DISCO strategies and dedicated to outreach WP7 will ensure that the changing needs of the project as well as its stakeholders are appropriately addressed. Combined will maximise the project impact.

Objectives

The DISCO Plan was developed to ensure efficient use of resources and successful outreach of AI-Mind. The plan provides an overview of the key dissemination and communication objectives that the consortium wishes to achieve by implementing various communication and dissemination activities. The AI-Mind objectives have been set as S.M.A.R.T. (specific, measurable, achievable, relevant and time-bound) to bring structure and tractability together and to create a verifiable trajectory towards clear DISCO main goals.

Communication and Dissemination Activities

AI-Mind will raise awareness of the project and its results through target group-oriented activities. This external communication occurs in three dimensions: the project, the study and the community of people with dementia. The planned dissemination actions will ensure that the project results are public and available to stakeholders.

Monitoring and Evaluation

To assess the implementation and impact of these activities, all implemented measures will be monitored and documented to evaluate individual activities against the defined KPIs and to adjust where required. The DISCO Plan will be updated throughout the project to ensure the quality of the proposed actions and the related information.

1 What is the challenge and how do we address it?

According to the [World Health Organization \(WHO\)](#), dementia affects around 55 million people worldwide. Estimates show that, globally, nearly 9.9 million people develop dementia every year, which translates into one new case every three seconds. In the [Global action plan on the health public health response to dementia 2017-2025](#), the first action area refers to placing dementia as a health priority across the Member States.

Mild cognitive impairment (MCI) is the stage between normal brain ageing and dementia, and it affects up to 18% of people aged 60 or older. As a study shows, up to 50% of people with MCI are at risk of progressing to dementia within five years.¹ Furthermore, 50% of dementia cases globally are attributable to only seven risk factors: diabetes, hypertension, obesity, depression, physical inactivity, smoking and low education. All of these are largely modifiable.² Ninety-five percent of the public assume that they will develop dementia in their lifetime. More importantly, 82% of respondents indicated that they would take a genetic test to learn about their risk of developing dementia.³ Current clinical practice, however, lacks the necessary screening tools to identify those at risk. The patient's journey typically takes many years and involves several clinical visits before a conclusive diagnosis of dementia is finally reached. To ensure that patients receive prompt treatment, there is an urgent need to develop a method for an early and accurate estimation of dementia risk.

Proactive adaptation of traditional clinical MCI diagnostic procedures to the digital artificial intelligence (AI) age is therefore essential for the sustainability of European healthcare systems in the face of increasingly ageing societies and limited health budgets.

Dr Ira Haraldsen (OUS)
Project coordinator and lead for the concept governance and requirements of the AI-Mind tools

I hope that AI-Mind will contribute to the change in health system. By developing a new screening method we can make one step forward into taking care of our brain.

50M

People worldwide affected with dementia

2x

Expected increase in the number of people with dementia over the next 20 years

Figure 1 The first AI-Mind infographic addressing the public regarding the use of AI for dementia prevention.

1.1 About the AI-Mind project

The AI-Mind project is a five-year research and innovation action (RIA) that officially started in March 2021 with a consortium of 15 partners from eight European countries setting up a multidisciplinary approach to address the challenge of effective dementia prevention. Funded by the European Commission (EC) under the Horizon 2020 programme, the project has an initial budget of around EUR 14 million. AI-Mind brings together professionals from multiple sectors, including academic institutions, medical centres, small and medium-sized enterprises, spin-off companies and patient associations, with a common goal of providing future patients with a better and personalised diagnosis.

Through international collaboration, consortium members will develop two AI-based tools: the AI-Mind Connector and the AI-Mind Predictor. These two tools will process routinely collected data in an innovative way. The AI-Mind Connector, which is fed with brain images from electroencephalographic (EEG) data, will evaluate and visualise interactions between different brain areas, identifying early disturbances in the functional brain network. AI-Mind reads these disturbances as the first signs of cognitive changes that may develop into dementia in the future. The AI-Mind Predictor, which makes use of AI to combine data from the Connector, cognitive tests and blood analysis, will provide an accurate (>95%) prediction of dementia risk for clinical decision making. Both tools will be integrated into a cloud-based diagnostic platform, providing an easy-to-implement service for health professionals. The AI-Mind solution will be tested and validated through a research study involving 1,000 participants with MCI in five European clinical centres:

- Hospital Clínico San Carlos (Madrid, Spain)
- Meilahden sairaala - Meilahti Hospital (Helsinki, Finland)
- Oslo University Hospital (Oslo, Norway)
- IRCCS, San Raffaele Roma (Rome, Italy)
- Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore – Policlinico Universitario A. Gemelli (Rome, Italy)

Using the tools described above, AI-Mind will enable doctors to significantly delay patients' loss of autonomy in daily activities and improve the lives of patients and caregivers. The ongoing coronavirus pandemic underlines the significant vulnerability of people affected by dementia (due to, e.g., the need for isolation of demented individuals, infection prophylaxis and reduced emotional contact with caregivers) and the urgent need for early detection and intervention. Currently, an ongoing AI revolution is redefining the health sector. Personalised and precise healthcare is on the verge of advancing from concept to reality, and the EC emphasises 'how artificial intelligence and supercomputing offer new opportunities to transform healthcare' in the [EC White Paper on Artificial Intelligence](#) published in February 2020. However, the everyday situation of performing dementia risk evaluations in clinics around Europe deviates significantly from the European ambition to use advanced predictive and preventive diagnosis and intervention methods. The first AI-Mind infographic (Figure 1) presents an overview of the current practice and AI-Mind methods, innovations and envisioned impact.

1.2 Project goals

Using the AI-Mind Connector and Predictor, which provide a fast and accurate prediction for the individual dementia risk, AI-Mind aims to radically shorten a patient's journey that can take several years with the current medical practice. This contribution to the health system would give doctors and patients a window for preventive interventions, therapies and rehabilitation measures early in the course of the disease.

AI-Mind aims specifically to do the following:

- ✓ Deliver timely and reliable dementia risk estimations with the use of AI tools
- ✓ Provide treatment effect evaluations before the onset of dementia
- ✓ Increase the screening rate for MCI
- ✓ Strengthen research & innovation capacity across Europe
- ✓ Contribute to a sustainable health system
- ✓ Reduce the cost and burden of dementia by introducing a way for timely intervention
- ✓ Deliver a health technology assessment (HTA) to enhance the innovation of predictive medicine in dementia

1.3 AI-Mind solution strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats

A SWOT analysis facilitates the development of a plan for communication and dissemination and indicates key points to consider when defining a framework and strategies for communication and dissemination. The **strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats** of the AI-Mind solution (Figure 2) have been analysed carefully to ensure that the expected project results meet project objectives and stakeholders’ needs. The strengths and opportunities of AI-Mind outweigh the weaknesses and threats, so there is a high chance of user acceptance and of our approach and technologies becoming a clinical reality.

Figure 2 AI-Mind SWOT analysis included in the proposal and further in “Description of Actions”, an official document elaborating the scope of the project, involved parties, objectives and implementation of actions.

2 Why do we need a dissemination and communication plan?

Researchers, including those involved in AI-Mind, have the advantage of being at the forefront of scientific progress. However, as this advantage is financed through public funding, in this case under the Horizon 2020 EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (R&I), scientists also have an obligation to communicate their work to a wide range of audiences, share their knowledge and ensure that the project’s results are disseminated to those who may use them to further advance R&I.

Considering that dissemination and communication are two ways in which EU-funded projects generate impact, they comprise different elements, have different objectives and address different audiences. In both instances, however, poor execution adds to the project’s failure and consequently puts the EU investment at risk. For this reason, the EU requires that DISCO measures are already included in a project proposal to be evaluated, making them an important and inseparable part of the project. To ensure efficient use of resources and successful outreach, the AI-Mind consortium has developed a DISCO plan that includes objectives, strategy and key messages, tools and channels used in communication, as well as an overview of planned activities, their implementation and evaluation procedures.

Following the AI-Mind lifecycle of sixty months and reporting periods, the **DISCO strategy is based on four phases** shown below and described further in the “Implementation” chapter (Section 6). This process will ensure that the changing needs of both the project and its stakeholders are appropriately addressed.

Prof. Hanna Renvall (HUH)
Leader for data management and features extraction

In AI-Mind, we have an incredible opportunity to bring together partners with expertise in different disciplines and combine methods used in different places.

2.1 The purpose of the plan

Employing best practices and in accordance with the EC [guidance on how to communicate EU R&I projects](#), AI-Mind's DISCO plan has been strategically designed to provide the following:

- An outline of communication and dissemination objectives and strategies
- An overview of key messages and target audiences
- An explanation of the relationship and differences between audiences, messages, channels and tools, materials and activities
- A portfolio of DISCO activities planned throughout the project
- An explanation of monitoring means used for the evaluation of AI-Mind DISCO performance

2.2 Methodology

AI-Mind partners performed a situation analysis during the proposal preparation phase, which included the following: (i) a SWOT (Section 1.3) analysis; (ii) external factors, via a political, economic, social, technological, environmental and legal (PESTEL) analysis; (iii) benchmarking AI-Mind to other EU projects; and (iv) the initial identification of stakeholders. These actions helped to better understand the needs of both the project and the various target groups and to choose comprehensive means to appropriately address different expectations. The collected data served as a basis for the AI-Mind DISCO Plan, which was developed collectively by the consortium partners between months eight and twelve of the project (M8-13) under the lead of [accelopment Schweiz AG](#) (accelCH). accelCH is one of the leading companies in the EU successfully supporting international consortia in project management, [communication and dissemination](#). As a consortium, we have chosen to develop the DISCO plan methods that applied best practices for co-creation and helped generate ideas and produce added value. These methods include the following:

- Regular brainstorming meetings within Work Package 7 (WP7) and three sessions with other WPs
- Co-working sessions in an online environment
- Data collection through specially designed documents, so-called "input collectors"
- Sharing Microsoft Office-based documents with project partners via email and through a cloud-based internal platform provided by accelCH to all consortium members, accelCLOUD
- In-person sessions at the 3rd General Assembly meeting, including personal interviews.

As further described in this document, AI-Mind DISCO objectives (Section 2.3) will be met thanks to tailored strategies (Section 3) and the use of cross-channel communication (Section 4). These will be put in use when implementing various activities (Section 5). As part of the DISCO plan, the consortium also developed an implementation pathway according to the project lifecycle (Section 6.1). Furthermore, the performance of all activities will be continuously monitored and all actions evaluated (Section 7).

2.3 Objectives

Based on the definitions shown in Figure 3, the chosen methodology has helped the consortium to define clear objectives and tailor strategies for both communication and dissemination and to better plan all outreach activities according to the project timeline and EU guidelines. In general, through **communication** that focuses on promoting the project and its results and **dissemination**, which ensures project results are public and available for use, AI-Mind will increase the impact and safeguard meeting the project’s goals. Considering these, the key AI-Mind DISCO objectives are listed below.

Communication

involves taking measures to promote the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, possibly through a two-way exchange, with the main aim to reach out to society as a whole to highlight the benefits of the action and how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges.

Dissemination

is defined as the public disclosure of the action’s results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results). It aims to transfer results to the ones who can make best use of them and to maximise the impact of research.

Figure 3 Definition of communication and dissemination considered by AI-Mind.

Communication objectives

- ✓ Explain the rationale of AI-Mind.
- ✓ Generate visibility of the project and its progress to all AI-Mind stakeholders.
- ✓ Raise awareness through public engagement on MCI, dementia, risk factors and the importance of early prediction.
- ✓ Demonstrate the importance of collaboration as a way of achieving scientific breakthroughs that benefit society.
- ✓ Inform potential participants of the AI-Mind study about the inclusion and exclusion criteria, the procedures and how to enrol in the study at one of five study sites.

Dissemination objectives

- ✓ Share knowledge on the use of sensitive health data in Europe.
- ✓ Share knowledge on the scientific and technical basis of AI tools for dementia risk estimation and prediction.
- ✓ Facilitate the uptake of project results by the scientific community, policymakers and industry.
- ✓ Contribute to strengthening European R&I capacity.
- ✓ Enhance partner’s reputation and visibility at local, national and international levels.
- ✓ Ensure collaboration for follow-up R&I initiatives.

Besides the objectives listed above, AI-Mind has two other important aims related to communication, dissemination and community building:

- AI-Mind will empower people by increasing their knowledge about MCI, dementia and importance of early intervention. AI-Mind will do so by providing adequate information on the potential to optimise their individual risk. In this way, sustainable behaviour change will be given special focus.
- AI-Mind will ensure the involvement of relevant stakeholders and provide a coherent set of recommendations and guidelines for public health authorities. In that regard, the involvement of partners such as Alzheimer Europe (AE) and the patients’ organisation on the European level will help ensure the interest of the vulnerable group of people with MCI or dementia.

2.4 Framework for EU project dissemination and communication

The DISCO Plan gives structure to AI-Mind dissemination and communication-related aspects and serves as a guide to all partners to transform their work, achievements and research results into an impact by meeting DISCO objectives. The overall AI-Mind DISCO framework builds on five key elements, as shown in Figure 4:

Figure 4 AI-Mind DISCO Plan framework conditions inspired by the Situation analysis, Objectives, Strategy, Tactic&Action and Control (SOTAC) model.

3 What are our communication and dissemination strategies?

As the EC emphasises, there is an enormous difference between communication strategically planned and ad hoc efforts for the sake of meeting contractual requirements.⁴ Strategic communication will help the AI-Mind project to

- Draw the attention of national governments, regional authorities and other funding sources to the need for and ultimate benefits of the research;
- Attract the interest of potential partners for follow-up initiatives;
- Encourage talented scientists and students to join AI-Mind partners' institutes and enterprises;
- Enhance project partners' reputation and visibility at the local, national and international levels;
- Facilitate the exploitation of project results; and
- Generate market demand for the AI-Mind solution.

The AI-Mind DISCO practice combines **two key elements**: communication strategy and dissemination strategy. Although these approaches focus on different aspects, both make use of the identification of stakeholders and key messages and both both strengthen European capacity through collaboration.

Prof. Anis Yazidi
 (OsloMET)
 Leader of AI modelling
 for the AI-Mind
 Connector and Predictor

AI-Mind project is one of the largest projects joining neuroscience and AI in Europe and in the world. It is a truly interdisciplinary project.

3.1 Stakeholders

Ed Freeman (1984) defines stakeholders as “any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the organisation’s objectives”. Often these individuals change or their interests in the project change during the different phases of the project.⁵ Identifying stakeholders and their expectations is, therefore, an essential step in generating an impact. Additionally, several scholars (e.g. Caroll, 2015; Crane and Livesey 2003; Koschmann, 2016) have suggested that the crucial element of stakeholder relations is effective communication, AI-Mind partners have to be aware of whom exactly to address their messages. For that, the consortium followed a three-stage process, which included (1) identifying stakeholders and (2) analysing and (3) mapping the main groups of stakeholders on the influence/impact grid

3.1.1 Identification and analysis

Through brainstorming sessions, input compilation and lessons learned from other projects, AI-Mind partners were involved in sharing sufficient data and knowledge for the communication team to identify target groups and perform a profound analysis of the stakeholders. Those were divided into six clusters with sixteen main groups. During the process, it became clear that the high number of target audiences came from the interdisciplinarity of AI-Mind and its international dimension. To identify the stakeholders’ needs and expectations towards the project, the communication team collected further input from different experts involved in the project. An overview of the outcomes is presented in Table 1.

Additionally, we have broken down the main groups based on the stakeholders’ field of expertise, relationships towards people with MCI and/or dementia, research/business area and the geographical region, as shown in Annex 1, to help AI-Mind partners choose the right message, communication channel and tool, and to better tailor the outreach activity to the target audience.

Table 1 The AI-Mind stakeholders’ identification based on the sector, including a projection of their needs and expectations towards the project.

Cluster	The Main Stakeholders’ Group	Needs and Expectations
 Healthcare System	Clinics & hospitals involved in the project	Improved diagnostics tools and efficiency in providing services.
	Healthcare providers	Knowledge about MCI, timely intervention, etc.
	Health Technology Assessment (HTA) experts	Information about AI-based tools, new technologies and implementation in a clinical environment.
	Memory clinics at local and national levels in Norway, Finland, Italy & Spain	Information about the project, risk factors of dementia, knowledge about MCI.
	Insurance companies	Decreased spending on people with dementia. MCI early diagnosis can regulate the individual’s premiums.

<p>Patients' advocacy</p>	<p>Patients' associations at the European level</p>	<p>Knowledge of the risk factors and prevention</p>
	<p>Informal carers for people with dementia and MCI</p>	<p>Information about the MCI, project, improved quality of life</p>
	<p>People with MCI, dementia</p>	<p>Knowledge of the risk factors and prevention, improved quality of life and timely diagnosis</p>
<p>Science community</p>	<p>Educational institutions, including universities, technology and research organisations</p>	<p>Scientific collaboration, new knowledge, advancement in science</p>
	<p>EU R&I initiatives</p>	<p>Scientific collaboration, use of the project's results</p>
<p>Industry</p>	<p>Health diagnostics equipment manufacturers</p>	<p>Business opportunities improved service and used technology</p>
	<p>Pharma companies</p>	<p>Increased income, information about the innovations and knowledge on new diagnostics methods</p>
	<p>AI, Information Communication Technology (ICT) and data management providers</p>	<p>Information about the project results and applicability of methods for data management and AI</p>
<p>Regulatory bodies</p>	<p>Policymakers</p>	<p>Recommendations, guidelines</p>
	<p>Funding agencies on European and national levels</p>	<p>Digitalisation and technological progress, strengthened R&I capacity</p>
<p>Other relevant</p>	<p>The general public in Norway, Italy, Finland and Spain and on an international level</p>	<p>Information about dementia, risk factors, MCI, the AI-Mind project and the study</p>

Additionally, based on the input collected from the consortium members and desk search, the AI-Mind communication team included a social network analysis (SNA) in the analysis to identify correlations, define opportunities for network expansion and estimate the trajectory influencing the project.

3.1.2 Stakeholder mapping on the impact/influence matrix

To distinguish which target groups are of the highest importance to the AI-Mind consortium, all partners rated the main and sub-groups in “input collector”. Based on their responses regarding both the interest stakeholders may have in the AI-Mind project and the influence of these stakeholders on the project’s performance, we mapped the respective group on the influence/interest matrix as presented in Figure 5. The priority of addressing relevant target audiences was also assessed, providing information for the strategic planning of communication and dissemination activities. By mapping stakeholders’ interests in AI-Mind, partners get a clear view of which target groups their efforts should focus on. A good understanding of the stakeholders, including the preferred way of communication, will help AI-Mind better tailor messages addressed to a broad range of audiences.

Figure 5 AI-Mind stakeholders interest/influence matrix, including time priority (red – high priority, yellow – medium priority, green – low priority) in addressing relevant target audiences based on partners rating and performed analysis.

3.2 Key messages

Key messages of AI-Mind are the main points of information the consortium needs its audience to hear, understand and remember. In particular, AI-Mind partners should articulate the purpose of the project and the value it brings to the different target groups. Considering that stakeholders have different interests in the AI-Mind project, key messages need to be tailored to the specific expectations of their respective audiences. Appropriate messages will be defined and updated as needed throughout the project to suit the current stage of the project's progression and changing expectations of stakeholders. Nevertheless, all communication and dissemination activities will be developed around seven key messages:

- The tools developed in the project will use AI to screen the brain connectivity of people with MCI and to predict the risk of developing dementia.
- AI-Mind is an EU-funded project that strengthens R&I capacity through international collaborations and fosters breakthroughs in science that otherwise could not be achieved.
- AI-Mind raises awareness concerning the project with the general public and provides information on MCI, dementia, risk factors and the need for improved clinical practice.
- AI-Mind consortium paves the way for the implementation of other AI-based tools for neurodegenerative diseases.
- AI-Mind addresses the challenge of an ageing society and the health priority of neurodegenerative diseases, such as dementia and Alzheimer's disease.
- A key element of the project is a research study involving 1,000 participants recruited from four countries.
- AI-Mind contributes to a sustainable health system with reusable and open data.

3.3 AI-Mind communication strategy

3.3.1 Approach

From the three most common approaches to communication – linear, interactional and transactional⁶ – the AI-Mind communication team considered linear models the most appropriate for ensuring public engagement in AI-Mind communication. Although we acknowledge that some activities may follow the communication model of Shannon and Weaver (1949), the main system on which we developed the AI-Mind communication strategy is Berlo’s Sender, Message, Channel and Receiver (SMCR) model (1960) due to its consideration of additional factors that influence communication, such as awareness level, cultural and social system, and attitudes. Because AI-Mind is an international project involving partners from eight countries and an observational study that is taking place in four different language zones, we consider that communication differences may arise from regional-specific attitudes. Our communication, based on the SMCR model, is, hence, decentralised and includes activities performed by the consortium members at the national and local levels. Although the SMCR model is more comprehensive than other linear models, it doesn’t include feedback, which is, in both AI-Mind communication and dissemination, a crucial element for strengthening public engagement. Therefore, we added a feedback/evaluation loop to the process to improve outreach throughout the AI-Mind project and increase its impact (Figure 6).

Figure 6 The use of Berlo’s SMCR model in the AI-Mind communication strategy.

In general, the **sender**, i.e. the source of the message, is the AI-Mind Consortium; responsibilities are defined for each activity and assigned to individuals or groups involved in the project (Annex 5).

The **message** is dependent on the action, as these vary in formality and target audience. However, all need to align with AI-Mind’s key messages.

For each activity, the appropriate **channel and tool** that appears most suitable for delivering the message to the implied audience will be selected.

The **receiver** of the message is the target audience, which consists of specific individuals or groups. AI-Mind partners have to be aware that the **meaning**, that is, how the message is perceived, results not only from preceding steps but also from the context in which the message is placed. Moreover, although a message is implied towards a specific group, other audiences may receive the message and decode it otherwise than assumed.

To monitor and improve our strategy, performance metrics will be put in place for all activities, allowing us to evaluate their effectiveness based on **feedback** (direct and indirect).

3.3.2 Communication guidelines

One of the obligations included in the grant agreement (GA) that all EU-funded projects must respect is including the EU acknowledgement in all means of communication and dissemination. As much as it may seem to be a formality of the contractual agreement, it increases the visibility of European funding for the R&I and positions the project amid other initiatives that were chosen for their innovation and capacity to contribute to a better future and benefit society.

In addition, any communication activity must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the EC is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. All AI-Mind consortium members respect all obligations from Art. 38.1 of the GA and include in their communication both mandatory elements: the EU emblem and acknowledging statement. To facilitate the process of following the requirements of the EU, accelCH prepared the communication guidelines for AI-Mind partners, including the correct format of the EU acknowledgement. Furthermore, these guidelines became a part of the project Handbook (D8.1), which is available to all partners through accelCLOUD.

- **EU acknowledgement for communication**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 964220.

- **EU acknowledgement for infrastructure, equipment and major results**

This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 964220.

To ensure that communication materials developed throughout the project are consistent in style, the communication team defined typography rules to use in the abovementioned AI-Mind Handbook, as shown here:

Typography for print and digital

For communication materials in print and digital that serve promotion of project activities, the "Heebo" font should be used as a primary font for headings and text. As a secondary font, only for "body text" "Monsterrat" font can be used. For the Headings and subheadings, font colour is defined by AI-Mind logo:

 RGB 0 42 58
CMYK 100 33 6 84
PANTONE 303 C

The font sizes are predefined as follows:

HEADING FONT SIZE

(Heebo medium upper case 110% wide 18pt, 27pt line spacing)

Subtitle font size

(Heebo regular 110% wide 15pt 20pt line spacing)

Sample paragraph text in size 12pt.

(Heebo regular 107 % wide 12pt 16pt line spacing)

Sample paragraph text in size 10pt.

(Heebo regular 107 % wide 10pt 14pt line spacing)

Heebo font has been strategically chosen by the consortium due to its readability, appealing and clean form and professional character when displayed. This font will be used in different sizes for all communication materials, such as infographics, flyers, factsheets and banners, except for official documents; it is also set as the default font on the AI-Mind website. This internationally employed sans-serif font is available via an open-source licence and will support transporting the message to the respective target audience across Europe.

3.4 AI-Mind dissemination strategy

3.4.1 Approach

The dissemination activities will deal with the diffusion of research and scientific and technological knowledge generated within the context of the project, aiming to ensure both a mid- and long-term impact. AI-Mind will apply responsible research and innovation (RRI), an approach that anticipates and assesses potential implications and societal expectations with regard to R&I, to foster the design of inclusive and sustainable R&I. RRI has acquired prominence by its status as a “cross-cutting issue” of the EU framework programme for R&I, Horizon 2020,⁷ and it focuses on six dimensions: Public Engagement, Gender Equality, Science Education, Open Access, Ethics and Governance. All AI-Mind dissemination activities will be performed by all partners, according to each partner’s profile and expertise and in consideration of all six RRI dimensions.

3.4.2 Open access

The EC has facilitated the access and reuse of research data generated by European projects through the [Open Research Data \(ORD\) Pilot](#). Under Horizon 2020, participation in the pilot was voluntary and the AI-Mind consortium members were in favour of their participation. The consortium follows the [EU “Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020”](#). Therefore, AI-Mind will provide open access by allowing the end user free online and reusable access to scientific information. Broader access to scientific publications and data helps to improve the quality of results, avoid a duplication of effort, speed up innovation and improve the transparency of the scientific process. We envisage managing all research outputs (publications, data and other outputs) in line with the FAIR principles to facilitate their re-use in the future and to link dementia-related research. As per Art. 29 of the GA, all articles in peer-reviewed journals will be made accessible free of charge through either gold or green open access (Figure 7). AI-Mind will ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications and public deliverables.

Figure 7 Open access process to make AI-Mind results available.

3.4.3 FAIR principles

The increasing availability of online resources means that the data need to be created with longevity in mind. Providing other researchers with access to AI-Mind data will facilitate knowledge discovery and improve research transparency. Therefore, it is in the interest of all partners that the best use is made of data generated within the project. That being said, the **FAIR** principles need to be respected by all consortium members following the “[Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020](#)” published by the EC in 2016. The FAIR principles put specific emphasis on enhancing the ability of machines to automatically find and use the data, while supporting its reuse by individuals.⁸ Data must be **Findable** – make data discoverable with metadata and a standard identification mechanism (e.g. a DOI); **Accessible** – provide documentation and tools needed to access the data, and if certain datasets cannot be shared, provide a clear reason why that is; **Interoperable** – allow data exchange and re-use between researchers and institutions by using standardised metadata and methodologies; and **Reusable** – release data with a copyright licence that will clarify how data can be re-used, all to the greatest extent possible. FAIR data are easier to reuse and distribute because machines are then able to understand where the data is and what it is about. It also boosts research and facilitates reuse by different stakeholders.

3.5 Strengthening European capacity through collaborations

One of the key goals of funding programmes is to strengthen Europe’s innovation and scientific capacity and as the EC emphasises, only by linking Europe’s fragmented resources through cross-border digital infrastructure can significant breakthroughs in health be achieved. The AI-Mind consortium explores and, whenever the possibility arises, expands its network at the international, national and local levels to contribute to achieving this aim and harvest scientific breakthroughs. During the first year of the project, AI-Mind has already reported achievements through establishing several valuable collaborations:

- The [Human Brain Project](#) (HBP) is one of three European Future and Emerging Technology (FET) Flagship projects. With a [winning EBRAINS Research Infrastructure Voucher Call](#), AI-Mind became a [partnering project to the HBP](#). The EBRAINS Voucher makes possible the partnership of AI-Mind, TVB-Cloud and HBP – three important European initiatives in the digitalisation of the brain. The [Virtual Brain Cloud Project](#) (TVB-Cloud) is a programme of the European Open Science Cloud that develops virtual brain simulations. The collaboration of these initiatives not only aligns with the [European Digital Health strategy](#) in using digital technologies for the benefit of patients, but it is also the first with the potential to take a critical step towards an AI revolution in brain healthcare.
- Collaboration with other EU-funded projects is envisioned. For example, mutual participation in the events organised by AI-Mind and [BRAINTEASER](#), a project that seeks to exploit the value of big data in healthcare, has been discussed. The dimensions of this collaboration will be further explored.

AI-Mind consortium members with well-established local networks will also seek collaborations at the national and local levels, including ones with patient organisations, memory clinics and other institutions that may improve AI-Mind’s impact.

4 How do we ensure efficient communication?

The discourse of science mistrust that was perpetuated during the COVID-19 pandemic⁹ revealed the importance of the dialogue between science and society. Scientific communication is used to communicate new knowledge mostly through scientific papers, technical reports and presentations at conferences to an audience of researchers, scientists and technical experts. More and more is expected of scientists, however, to expand boundaries and apply other methods of communication about their research.

The EU expects researchers to inform, educate and raise awareness of science-related topics among a broad range of audiences. Scientists and international consortia must therefore choose wisely the ways in which they plan to reach the public and define the best tools that support conveying their messages. In health projects involving recruitment to various research studies, trustworthiness is an aspect that may affect the project's progress. Therefore, the choice of communication channels and tools is even more significant, as these influence how the project is perceived. To address this challenge, AI-Mind applies cross-channel and multimedia approaches to external communication.

AI-Mind's tactic includes the project's visual identity, communication channels and tools for both internal and external communication as well as application-specific materials. As both channels and tools are used in the communication process, there is a fair overlap. The difference is mainly seen in the role both elements have in the act.

Dr José M. Peña (Lurtis)
 Leader of the data analysis and interactive visualisation platform

AI-Mind is special because it is a joint effort in which academia and industry may contribute to the early detection of dementia and have a great impact on the quality of life of people affected with cognitive decline.

Channels

Methods used to convey the message. In the SMCR communication model, these are categorised based on the senses people use in the act.

Tools

Format in which the message is packed that supports passing the message through the chosen channel.

Materials

Means that make use of different channels and tools which are categorised based on their application.

4.1 Visual identity

Visual identity establishes a framework for creating an impression and shaping the perception of the AI-Mind project through visible elements. Following the SMCR communication model, the AI-Mind consortium has chosen elements that can be easily decoded across multicultural audiences, regardless of their attitude, knowledge, social system, culture or communication skills. Consequently, the AI-Mind logo (Figure 8) was carefully designed considering its semiotics and semantics. The logo is composed of two elements: text and the representation of a puzzle constructed in the shape of a human’s head. Despite the text being written in English “AI-Mind”, the visual element is easily decoded as signifiers for “mind/head” and “puzzled” or “troubled”, conveying the key message about the area of the action.

Figure 8 AI-Mind logo in colour (on the left) and in the grey scale (on the right).

The colours used in the AI-Mind logo were strategically chosen based on colour psychology, including emotional inclinations and cultural aspects on both the sender’s and receiver’s sides. Research shows that 98 languages have words for the same 11 basic colours.¹⁰ Although the meaning the colour may have can be very different depending on geographic area, in all eight countries where AI-Mind beneficiaries are located, interpretation of employed blue and green is alike, namely:

RGB 0 61 90
 CMYK 1 32 0 65
 #003D5A

Blue is typically associated with trust, focus, knowledge and reliability and is therefore often used in health-related logos. Blue has also been proven to be one of the most liked colours worldwide.

RGB 49 116 84
 CMYK 58 0 28 55
 #317454

Green is the most common colour in the natural world and it’s the second most-liked colour worldwide. Green is mostly associated with health, vitality, growth and progress-thinking.

Moreover, based on logo colours, complementary and analogous colours were defined (Figure 9) to make the communication materials more appealing to the targeted audiences. To ensure a uniform appearance of the AI-Mind project across channels, outlets and locations, the described visual items and rules have been provided to the consortium members as part of the project handbook. These specifications need to be applied by partners in all DISCO means, including presentations, online and printed documents (factsheets, brochures, flyers) and publications related to the project.

RGB 226 224 252
 CMYK 9 0 0 0
 #e2f4fc

RGB 245 245 247
 CMYK 3 1 1 0
 #f5f7f7

RGB 0 152 222
 CMYK 75 27 0 0
 #0098de

RGB 0 82 120
 CMYK 98 67 32 14
 #005278

RGB 0 42 58
 CMYK 0 30 20 0
 #f77968

RGB 247 191 79
 CMYK 3 26 80 0
 #f7bf4f

Figure 9 AI-Mind visual identity – analogous and complementary colours to AI-Mind logo.

4.2 Communication channels and tools

The key to effective communication is to match the communication channel with the goal of the message.¹¹ Following the SCMR communication model, communication channels are categorised based on the senses engaged in decoding the message.

Communication channels are thus divided into **three principal channels**:

The principal communication channels will be used by the AI-Mind consortium and its members in digital and nondigital formats, depending on the tools used to convey the message. For example, audio-visual means of communication due to technicalities (the use of software to hear and see) enforce the digital dimension of this verbal communication channel. The digital formats retain the main characteristics of the principal channels but influence different aspects of each channel – verbal, written and nonverbal – in a new way.

The above communication channels will be employed by the AI-Mind consortium and its members in both direct and indirect communication acts. Often, more than one channel will be used at the same time to strengthen the message or increase the engagement of the audience.

It is also worth mentioning that different factors influence the methods implied in the communication activity. For example, the level of English may affect the way the message is transmitted through a **verbal channel**, either at consortium meetings or when interacting with audiences at AI-Mind events. Although the use of **written channels** suggests that the content can be constructed over a longer period of time with greater attention to detail, it also involves risks. The terminology applied when communicating is one of the challenges, as a single word may be understood (decoded) differently by a clinician and an AI expert. With the use of **nonverbal channels**, attention is shifted towards visual attributes for remote communication and paralanguage, as well as body language for in-person interaction. Considering these factors, the AI-Mind consortium will continuously identify risks arising from implemented channels and address them. This will be done in two ways:

- Using the most appropriate tools will decrease the inconvenience of the channel; for example, a glossary of terms can be produced and shared within and beyond the consortium by incorporating them into deliverables and other reports.
- Processes that ensure high-quality communication, including internal reviews of produced materials or tests of infrastructure, will be used in DISCO activities.

4.2.1 Internal

EU-funded projects bring together experts from various fields from different backgrounds and cultures, making it challenging to ensure efficient collaboration – one of the key elements that safeguards the success of the project. Efficient collaboration is also one of the strategic aims of the AI-Mind consortium. For this reason, a cloud-based collaboration platform has been created and provided by accelCH, offering each partner independent access to important documents, including meeting minutes, deliverables, agendas, contracts, mailing lists, the communication and dissemination tracking tool, presentations, templates, supporting materials and other miscellaneous project information. Access to the platform is restricted to consortium members, who can log in with their personal passwords. Compiling different channels, accelCLOUD serves as a tool that facilitates information exchange. Methods of communication between partners comprise various channels, including those presented in Table2.

	 non-verbal		
AI-Mind examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consortium meetings (in-person, online), including management meetings (on a weekly or bi-weekly basis), executive board meetings (monthly), WP meetings (on-demand depending on WP progress and needs) • Calls (phone, video) • Talks • Presentations and webinars 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emails • Documents • Messages • Codes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pictures • Figures • Flowcharts • Graphic elements • Icons and symbols

Table 2 Examples of communication channels in AI-Mind internal communication.

4.2.2 External

All channels that are used for reaching beyond the consortium members and, according to DISCO objectives, are considered external. The project website combines different methods for reaching target audiences and makes use of all principal channels. Similar to internal accelCLOUD, the project website serves as a tool that supports communication about the project and the dissemination of its results beyond the AI-Mind network and facilitates engagement with all stakeholders.

	 non-verbal		
AI-Mind examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Videos (interviews, explanatory videos) • Webinars and workshops • Talks • Symposia • Conferences • Network meetings • Presentations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Texts (for press releases, news posts, articles, social media or blog posts) • Newsletters • Factsheets • Brochures • Publications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Photos • Figures • Flowcharts • Infographics

Table 3 Examples of communication channels in AI-Mind external communication.

4.3 Materials

4.3.1 Templates

To support the official communication of the AI-Mind project during events and meetings and to ensure the consistent style of developed reports, a uniform slide master on PowerPoint and templates on Word have been created. The design of these is based on the visual identity of the AI-Mind and aims for the best functionality. Each template can be easily customised with partners' data and content except for elements in PowerPoint that are fixed and cannot be modified, such as the EU acknowledgement and the AI-Mind logo.

The following templates are available to all partners on accelCLOUD:

- Deliverable template
- Meeting agenda template
- Meeting minutes template
- PowerPoint presentation template

- Scientific poster template (Figure 10)

Poster Print Size:
This poster template is set up for DIN A0 international paper size of 841 mm x 1189 mm (portrait). It can be printed at 70.6% for an A1 poster of 594 mm x 841 mm.

Placeholders:
Feel free to edit, move, add, and delete items, or change the layout to suit your needs. Always check with your conference organizer for specific requirements.

Font:
Consider font size and the amount of text on your poster; less text is preferred. Use a font size of at least 24 point, but 32 point and larger is recommended. Do not use all capital letters for emphasis. Italics, underlining, shadows, outlines, etc., are difficult to read. Bold can be effective if used consistently and simply.

Image Quality:
You can place digital photos or logo art in your poster file by selecting the **Insert, Picture** command, or by using standard copy & paste. For best results, all graphic elements should be at least 150-200 pixels per inch (ppi) in their final printed size. For instance, a 1600 x 1200 pixel photo will usually look fine up to 20-25cm wide on your printed poster.

To preview the print quality of images, select a magnification of 100% when previewing your poster. This will give you a good idea of what it will look like in print

[This sidebar area does not print.]

The poster template includes the following sections and content:

Template To Be Used For AI-Mind Posters

Replace This Text With Your Title

Partner Name, CO¹ John Doe, PhD²; Brendan Griffin, MD, PhD^{1,2}
¹University of Affiliation, ²Center of Affiliation

Oslo universitetssykehus

your name
your organization
email
phone

Abstract

Click here to insert your Abstract text. Type it in or copy and paste from your Word document or other source.

This text box will automatically re-size to your text. To turn off that feature, right click inside this box and go to **Format Shape, Text Box, Autofill**, and select the "Do Not Autofill" radio button.

To change the font style of this text box: Click on the border once to highlight the entire text box, then select whatever suits you. This text is called 36pt and is really read up to 1.2 meters away on an A0 poster. This is the minimum size. Do not go any smaller than that!

Zoom out to 100% to preview what this will look like on your printed poster.

Introduction

accelopment[®] has provided this template to assist AI-Mind project partners in preparation of a medical or scientific research poster.

The dimensions are set to DIN A0 international paper size (1189mm high by 841mm wide) but print can be scaled up or down in size to any dimensions with the same aspect ratio. For example, if you order an A1 poster using this template, your printer will print the file at 70.6% of its original size.

The most critical factor is that your template and poster dimensions must be proportional:

$$\frac{\text{replace height}}{\text{template width}} = \frac{\text{desired print height}}{\text{desired print width}}$$

Methods

- Click here to insert your Methods and Materials text. Type it in or copy and paste from your Word document or other source.
- This text box will automatically re-size to your text.
- You may include a clear chart here if the amount of text allows it.
- Substit: make your text stand out

Chart 1. Substit 36pt Callus.

Heading	Heading	Heading
Substit	36pt	40pt
Substit	24pt	28pt
Substit	18pt	20pt

DATA POINT

AI-Mind Connector
Fully automated monitoring of human brain connectivity

AI-Mind Predictor
Assessing risks of developing dementia

RESULTS

Click here to insert your Results text. Type it in or copy and paste from your Word document or other source.

This text box will automatically re-size to your text. To turn off that feature, right click inside this box and go to **Format Shape, Text Box, Autofill**, and select the "Do Not Autofill" radio button.

To change the font style of this text box: Click on the border once to highlight the entire text box, then select whatever suits you. This text is called 36pt and is really read up to 1.2 meters away on an A0 poster.

Zoom out to 100% to preview what this will look like on your printed poster.

CONCLUSIONS

Click here to insert your Conclusions text. Type it in or copy and paste from your Word document or other source.

This text box will automatically re-size to your text. To turn off that feature, right click inside this box and go to **Format Shape, Text Box, Autofill**, and select the "Do Not Autofill" radio button.

To change the font style of this text box: Click on the border once to highlight the entire text box, then select whatever suits you. This text is called 36pt and is really read up to 1.2 meters away on an A0 poster. This is the minimum size. Do not go any smaller than that!

Zoom out to 100% to preview what this will look like on your printed poster.

References

1. Substit 36pt Callus.

2. Substit 36pt Callus.

Figure 10 Template for the scientific poster of AI-Mind.

4.3.2 Application specific

The channel used for individual communication or dissemination activity determines which medium is most appropriate for inclusion in the act. The AI-Mind consortium members have a wide spectrum of materials to choose from to strengthen the message. It's worth mentioning that content, precise message and language ought to be tailored to the audience by AI-Mind partners, whereas nonverbal aspects (images, colours, icons) should be consistent with AI-Mind's visual identity. For example, scientific posters created for the conference bringing together experts in neuroscience will employ a different language than a poster to be presented at AI-Mind dementia events targeting the general public. Nevertheless, printed material that effectively conveys the message is a valid tool for both groups. Depending on the application, we have produced a variety of materials to influence target groups, including the following:

- Corporate materials (logos, design guidelines, templates)
- Manuals (software, project handbook, AI-Mind tools instructions)

- Content material (publications and presentations, press releases, articles, posts, reports, news)
- Print material (factsheets, flyers, banners, posters)
- Audio/visual material (videos, images, infographics, cards)

As part of the governance, all partners will ensure that images used in AI-Mind communications will be published with Creative Commons licences, or, following the [EC Copywrite rules](#), will appropriately credit the author of the photo/image/graphic.

5 What do we do to reach our communication and dissemination objectives?

The responsible communication of science has always been an important issue for scientists, but it has gained even more attention during the past few years because of the COVID-19 pandemic. Through the EU R&I programme Horizon 2020, under which AI-Mind has received funding, the EU has committed to spending nearly EUR 80 billion on R&I over seven years. A [special Eurobarometer report](#) (2014) was developed to provide insights into which areas European citizens would like scientific research to focus on in the next 15 years. Health and medical care were the most mentioned priorities. A survey from 2021 [on European citizens' knowledge and attitudes towards science and technology](#) shows that 86% of respondents think that the overall influence of science and technology is positive and 61% expect AI to have a positive effect in the future. Health and medical care are seen as areas where science and technology can impact the most and at the same time, 86% of respondents are interested in new medical discoveries. AI-Mind is committed to strengthening public engagement in R&I projects through different DISCO activities tailored to various target audiences.

The external communication of AI-Mind occurs in three dimensions: the project, the study and the community of people with dementia. Besides communication activities, strategically chosen dissemination actions will ensure that project results are made public and available to stakeholders.

Prof. Paolo Maria Rossini (IRCCS)
Lead for the clinical implementation of AI-Mind tools

We must realise that being able to prolong full or partial autonomy in daily activities of elderly patients would be a goal of unparalleled importance for everyone, from Alzheimer's patients to their families and caregivers, and society itself.

Areas where science and technology can make the most difference according to respondents of the survey in 2021 are health and climate.

47%
Health and medical care

40%
The fight against climate change

5.1 AI-Mind communicates about the project

5.1.1 Website

Target group

healthcare system, patients' advocacy, science community, industry, regulatory bodies, other (general public)

Needs addressed

information about the project, knowledge about AI and HTA, knowledge about risk factors, knowledge about MCI

With over 460,000,000 internet users in the European Union alone,¹² a website can be a powerful instrument to communicate and spread information. The project website serves as an important multichannel that allows the AI-Mind consortium to raise awareness of the project and to provide up-to-date, consistent and complete information to its various stakeholders. The [AI-Mind](#) website has been evaluated and reviewed by partners before going live. A dedicated deliverable was produced (D7.1), which explains in detail the structure of the AI-Mind website, its design, its governance and maintenance. The deliverable also gives an overlook of the planned changes and highlights its objectives, as follows:

- Facilitate information about cognitive decline and MCI
- Raise awareness of the project and keep stakeholders engaged through tailored content
- Present the project partners and establish a network of experts in relevant fields
- Provide information and increase interest in AI-Mind events and other undertakings
- Inform potential participants about the AI-Mind study and facilitate contact with the local study team
- Create an engaging platform for knowledge sharing – the AI-Mind Knowledge Hub (Section 5.5)
- Offer the possibility of contacting the AI-Mind consortium directly

To ensure that the website aligns with AI-Mind objectives and meets the expectations of different stakeholder groups, the website content and its structure are tailored to the main target audiences. The easy-to-grasp navigation pane allows visitors to select the page of interest. The AI-Mind website will be updated throughout the project not

KPI

approx. 500 visitors/month

Figure 11 AI-Mind website menu and structure.

only in terms of the content, but also its structure, depending on the project and stakeholders' changing needs. The first restructuring was done in months (M) 6-10 due to the AI-Mind study starting in M12. During this modification, **the study pages** were developed in English for target audiences, potential participants and health professionals (Section 5.2.2).

The consortium employs various channels to reinforce the message and stimulate the different senses of the receiver to make the experience of interacting with AI-Mind nothing but meaningful. The website is considered a multichannel website as it employs all three **verbal** (video interviews, webinars), **written** (articles, text) and **nonverbal** (visual elements, pictures, animations) channels, which serve different purposes: verbal channels support knowledge sharing, written channels inform about the project, its progress and the consortium, and visual channels strengthen the emotional reception of the content (Figure 12).

We are looking for people with mild cognitive impairment (MCI) who are willing to take part in a large European study

Figure 12 Banner for the AI-Mind study pages.

The next update of the AI-Mind website is planned in M14-M24 and it will include the development of a structure for an area dedicated to knowledge sharing, AI-Mind Knowledge Hub (Section 5.4.5). Once a considerable number of results are available, including public deliverables, scientific publications, reports, presentations and other data, these will also be made available through the AI-Mind website under “Results”. Therefore, it’s envisioned that another modification to the website may be required in the second phase of the communication strategy and the next one in the fourth stage.

5.1.2 Social media

As statistics show in the EU,¹³ 57% of people aged 16-74 made use of social networks in 2020. Moreover, Facebook is often used by elderly people, with 62% of seniors aged 65+ who are on the platform and 72% of people between the ages of 50 and 64.¹⁴ Considering that one of the inclusion criteria for the AI-Mind study is the age range of people aged 65-80, Facebook is an effective tool to increase the project’s outreach. Moreover, social media arises from highly interactive platforms where users can share and discuss specific topics. These platforms provide individuals with a way of maintaining and strengthening social ties as they are able to connect with people all over the world and are seen by the EC as a useful tool to increase the impact of R&I projects. In the “[Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects](#)” published by the EC in 2020, one way of incorporating social networks into the outreach strategy is by recruiting volunteers/participants for the study.

Target group

healthcare system, patients’ advocacy, science community, industry, regulatory bodies, other (general public)

Needs addressed

information about the project, knowledge about AI and HTA, knowledge about risk factors, knowledge about MCI, dementia and early prediction, community building

AI-Mind will use social media platforms to raise awareness about the project and its activities and to disseminate its results. Moreover, clinical sites will include social media in local recruitment strategies, as described in Section 3.6.

After the EC guidelines, the AI-Mind project’s social media strategy covers where, who, how, what and when.

Where?

AI-Mind will use the most popular social networks, which can be easily accessed by common search engines or through the project website. Due to their own specifications, the content for AI-Mind posts will be adapted to each social media channel and the message will be tailored to the target audience.

Twitter: An online social media network where users interact with short messages due to the character limit of 280. Twitter is especially useful for reaching out to the general public, policymakers, researchers, civil society, scientific community or journalists and provides excellent evaluation opportunities. All consortium members were asked to follow the AI-Mind Twitter handle (@AIMind_eu) to increase the visibility of the project.

KPIs

500 followers per account, 20 shares/comments per post, 80 posts per account, 50 video views

Facebook: A social networking service and website where different types of users may create a personal profile, add other users as friends and exchange messages. Users may also join common interest user groups. The AI-Mind Facebook page (@AIMindEU) will be used to post the latest news of the project to reach the general public, civil society and researchers.

LinkedIn: A business-oriented social networking site that can be used for networking between individuals and groups. The AI-Mind page (@The AI-Mind Project) will be used to post the latest news on the project to reach out to the researchers and the industry. Sharing recent project publications and congratulating the authors (by tagging them) will also contribute to increasing the visibility of recent research and promoting EU initiatives.

YouTube: A video-sharing website on which users can upload, share and view videos. YouTube can also be used for sharing public video presentations. All the videos developed by the AI-Mind consortium will be uploaded to the AI-Mind YouTube channel (@The AI-Mind Project) to reach civil society, researchers and the general public.

Who?

Together with OUS, accelCH is responsible for setting up and maintaining AI-Mind’s social media accounts throughout the project duration. All partners will contribute to these by informing accelCH about any achievements and produced results of AI-Mind and by sharing information on dementia prediction and relevant initiatives that may be of interest to our stakeholders. AE’s well established presence on Twitter and Facebook and their network of local groups will maximise the outreach.

How?

Growing community on social networks is challenging for research projects and often the efforts invested don't produce the desired results. As part of the mitigating action, we defined the following processes that will be implemented:

- Consortium members with social media accounts will be able to post the contents of the AI-Mind Facebook, Twitter or Linked pages, mention the page, insert the official hashtag, #aimindproject, and point at the official website: ai-mind.eu.
- Partners' institutions and individuals, upon consent, will be tagged (@) in the AI-Mind posts. A list of handles has been developed for the consortium and will be continuously updated throughout the project.
- Relevant handles (@) and hashtags (#) will be included in social media posts linking it to a bigger context, for example, #FightingDementia [#Alzheimer](#) [#HealthUnion](#). A list of relevant hashtags has been developed and will be continuously updated throughout the project.
- Considering that >65% of people are visual learners and that the brain only needs 13 milliseconds to identify images,¹⁵ it is planned that every post produced by the AI-Mind will be complemented with a visual that strengthens the message.
- Use every opportunity that arises from international initiatives in the field of dementia, neurosciences, EU R&I or other, including [World Alzheimer's Month \(#WorldAlzMonth\)](#), [Brain awareness Week](#), [International Day of Women and Girls in Science](#).
- Follow other EU-funded R&I projects' social media accounts, such as [EBRAINS](#) and [Human Brain Project](#), and share relevant posts.
- The main language used for social media posts is English. However, following the SMCR model, it's envisioned that some content from AI-Mind may be translated by partners and posted in their local language. Also, to ensure that the required number of participants is enrolled in the study, whenever clinical sites use social networks as a part of the recruitment strategy, the content will be prepared in either Norwegian, Spanish, Italian or Finnish.
- Publish posts from AI-Mind in area-specific groups. We identified the following groups of interest in the AI-Mind project:

Artificial Intelligence & Deep Learning	Neuroscience, Neurophysics,
Cognitive Neuroscience	Neuroinformatics, Neuroethics,
Cognitive Science	Neurology
Data Science World	Online Society for Research in Cognition,
Digital Health	Neuroscience, and Psychology
Digital Health Platforms	Planet Neurology - Neuroscience -
Global Neuroscience Researchers	Neurosurgery - Neuropharmacology
Health research	Psychology and Neuroscience
Health Research and Technology	Psychology and Neuroscience
Neurology & Neuroscience	RESEARCH
Neuroscience	Research & Innovation
Neuroscience News and Research group	Senescence: the Issues of Aging

What?

With each social media platform, we target different audiences, as described above. In the first year of the project duration, there has been improvement work to reach the right target, which will continue until the M19. The content will be more targeted as soon as each social network has reached a considerable number of followers and the first stakeholder register is finalised. We define thematic areas of the content as dementia prediction and risk factors, MCI, AI, prevention, eHealth, project advancement, digital and in-person events, specialised magazine articles, website updates, consortium and partners, collaborations, neurosciences and brain health. Due to specifications of the social media channels used and to increase interest from the audience by encouraging them to comment, like or share other forms of feedback, we plan specifically to incorporate the following elements into AI-Mind communication:

- **Combine text with image** – due to the limit of 280 characters, included keywords, hashtags and handles
- **Videos** – max length 2m20s, recommended less than 1 min
- **GIFs** – either prepared in advance or selected from Twitter library with relevance to the audience

- **Infographics** – post a snippet and link to the website or a full version
- **Charts** – information will be valuable, shareable and digestible
- **Mems** – only if timely and relevant (logo)
- **Blog header** as an image – link to the website (people, faces and text work well)

- **Banner image** – include logo, tagline, specific to AI-Mind aims and scope
- **Photos of influential figures, consortium members** – combined with quotes
- **SlideShare** – shared presentations or slide deck with audience
- **Short text** – limit of 3000 character

- **Banner image** – include logo, picture specific to AI-Mind aims and scope
- **Videos** – animated videos, interviews, recordings from webinars, workshops and seminars
- **Description** – include narration describing the video with consideration of the key words for the search engine

Figure 13 Elements to include in AI-Mind communications on social platforms.

When?

Throughout 2020 and into 2021, social media became more important than ever as a way for people to maintain instantaneous connection, stay up to date on the current situation and follow online events during the COVID-19 pandemic. Following the [analysis](#), AI-Mind will regularly post on social media, primarily at the times shown here:

	Tue, Wed & Fri 9:00-13:00	Tue & Thru 9:00-11:00 Wed 9:00-11:00	Tue & Thru 9:00-12:00 Wed 9:00-14:00

5.1.3 Digital publishing

Target group of the activity

healthcare system, patients' advocacy, science community, industry, regulatory bodies, other (general public)

Needs addressed

information about the project, knowledge about AI and HTA, knowledge about risk factors, knowledge about MCI

KPIs

48 articles/press releases

Graesser and Ottati¹⁶ describe narrative as having “privileged status” in human cognition. Narratives offer intrinsic benefits in each of the four main steps of processing information: motivation and interest, allocating cognitive resources, elaboration and transfer into long-term memory.¹⁷ An increasing number of studies show how narratives can be useful for developing trust with an audience, increasing knowledge retention and promoting the willingness of the audience to learn and take action. In view of this, AI-Mind will use the storytelling method as the most efficient method for increasing the project’s impact. The storytelling will be done through text-based assets produced throughout the project lifecycle, which will be tailored on both the message and language levels to the target group:

- Press releases:** These are official statements prepared on a particular topic over a longer period than news items due to the complexity and depth of information provided. As an example, the very first press release of the project highlighted the project objectives and its ambition and it was shared in very different outlets, such as the [AI-Mind website](#), [SCIENCEEX](#), [AE website](#), [CORDIS](#) and to increase outreach to the general public on [Medium](#). The latter is an open publishing platform where experts share their knowledge through storytelling and writing about their work. The project communication team always shares a press release with all partners to increase the outreach of such activities. All partners also make an effort to translate the original (English) into their respective language, [as this example shows](#).
- News items/articles:** News items and articles cover the basics of current events and factual information. The project website has a dedicated [news area](#), with a particular focus shared on the home page. Every month, at least one news item is published. Relevant milestones of the project, individual accomplishments (e.g. [Prof. Renvall from Helsinki University Hospital \(HUU\)](#), [leader of WP2, was listed as one of the most influential people in the health sector in 2021](#)) and organisation of webinars, amongst others, make for good reports of the project activities and biggest achievements.
- Digital stories:** This refers to all other than the above-described text-based communication measures in digital form produced by AI-Mind, such as blog posts or stories published on [Medium](#), an online publishing platform. We identified opportunities to outreach the AI-Mind stakeholders, notably the scientific community, health and technology industry, with this form of communication, which will stay complementary to the main channels for AI-Mind narratives. For example, the AI-Mind consortium will produce a blog post about the study to be published in M19 of the project on the [Cambridge Cognition official blog](#). This post will be made available to researchers from around the world, raising awareness about EU-funded projects and AI-Mind in particular.

Target group of the activity

healthcare system, patients' advocacy, science community, industry, regulatory bodies, other (general public)

Needs addressed

information about the project, knowledge about AI and HTA, knowledge about risk factors, knowledge about MCI

KPIs

2 internal newsletters /year
500 downloads/AE or external newsletter

5.1.4 Digital newsletters

AI-Mind will use the monthly AE newsletter throughout the project duration for external communication about the project's progress and achievements. AE circulates its newsletter by email to a large audience reaching around 11,000 people, including members of national Alzheimer's associations, researchers, clinicians, people with dementia, careers and policymakers. The AE newsletters are also accessible on the AE website. Moreover, sections of the AE Newsletter are also available on the "Media" page of the AI-Mind website.

AI-Mind will also release an internal newsletter quarterly, which will include recent project achievements, communication highlights (e.g. presentations at key events), the project management overview and a short update of each WP. This newsletter will be sent to the EU Project Officer and will be accessible to the AI-Mind consortium via the internal accelCLOUD platform. In the first year of the project, two such materials were developed (Figure 14).

Intelligent digital tools for screening of brain connectivity and dementia risk estimation in people affected by mild cognitive impairment (MCI)

AUGUST - DECEMBER 2021 HIGHLIGHTS

About AI-Mind

AI-Mind is a 5-year project, started in March 2021 and funded by European Union Horizon 2020 under grant agreement no 964220. Our goal is to develop intelligent digital tools for screening brain connectivity and dementia risk estimation in people affected by mild cognitive impairment (MCI). MCI, a condition intermediate between normal brain ageing and dementia, affects up to 18% of people age 60 or older. Up to 50% of people with MCI are at risk of progressing to dementia within 5 years. We already know that the risk of dementia can be reduced by adopting healthy lifestyle habits and managing treatable conditions such as diabetes and high blood pressure. We wish to equip health professionals with innovative tools that will enable timely diagnosis and extend a window for preventive interventions, therapies, and rehabilitation.

Recent achievements

- Cooperation with EBRAINS and Human Brain Project (HBP)**
 - AI-Mind was one of the innovative projects that won the third [EBRAINS voucher call](#). AI-Mind in cooperation with [The Virtual Brain Cloud \(TVB-Cloud\)](#) will develop and implement infrastructure features to enhance brain modeling and data sharing. Read more in our [press release](#).
 - OUS representing the AI-Mind project is one of the partners of [HealthDataCloud](#) - after winning the call for EBRAINS Service for Sensitive Data (SSD). Read more in our [news piece](#).
 - AI-Mind is featured as a partnering project on the [HBP website](#) and partners are included in the HBP associated partners' list.
- Data Protection Officers (DPO) forum**
 - A forum with Data Protection Officers and legal representatives from all clinical sites has been established.
 - The first meeting introduced the need to set the legal basis for data transfer. A series of meetings will follow to fully cover the topic, guarantee compliance to all applicable laws and regulations, and ensure the protection of the study participants' data and privacy.

AI-Mind communication and dissemination (DISCO) highlights

AI-Mind study webpages for [healthcare professionals](#) and potential participants in local languages (Finnish, Italian, Norwegian, Spanish) are live.

A study explanatory video in 5 different languages was produced and is available on the project website, as well as on the AI-Mind YouTube channel.

Project management overview

All project deliverables and milestones are listed in an excel-based tool managed by the management support team. This tool was created by accelCH to track and monitor the progress of the work plan.

All required deliverables were submitted and all milestones were achieved so far. At the moment, and within the first reporting period (01.03.2021-28.02.2022), 60% of deliverables were submitted and the remaining 40% are already being written. 64% of all milestones due in the first reporting period were already achieved, the remaining 36% are undergoing.

Deliverables submitted: 12 delivered, 8 yet to submit by M12

Milestones achieved: 7 achieved, 4 yet to achieve by M12

AI-Mind was presented by the project coordinator and showcased with an exhibition space at 31st Alzheimer Europe Conference. The event welcomed more than 600 online participants.

It's important to highlight that around 20% of all deliverables and milestones were already achieved in the first nine months of the project!

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 964220.

Confidential - do not share outside the AI-Mind consortium

Figure 14 AI-Mind internal newsletter with the project's highlights, December 2021.

Target group

healthcare system,
patients' advocacy,
science community,
industry, regulatory
bodies, other
(general public)

Needs addressed

information about
the project,
knowledge about AI and
HTA,
knowledge about risk
factors,
knowledge about MCI
and dementia

KPIs

10 videos developed

5.1.5 Video series

A series of informational videos will be developed by the consortium presenting the project activities and explaining MCI and dementia, aspects of early-onset to disease, biomarkers and prediction. The series will be tailored to the target audience to maximise outreach and will include presentations of WP leaders, interviews with AI-Mind partners and members of the advisory board. All productions will be made available through AI-Mind channels, such as the website and YouTube account. Moreover, all partners will be encouraged to share these within their networks.

5.1.6 Digital and print materials

Digital audio-visual material, including videos and explanatory animations, will be created to visualise complex information in a simple way. All material will be shared with the networks of clinicians, researchers, people with MCI and the general public through AI-Mind channels, including the project website. The first [explanatory video](#) was developed in M6-M10 (Section 5.2.2.2). Throughout the project duration, we will create various materials based on the project’s visual identity so that partners can distribute these in print and be made available online on the AI-Mind website as part of the [AI-Mind media kit](#). Such materials will include a flyer providing information on the AI-Mind study, a poster and a roll-up for use in hospitals and during events, infographics targeting people with MCI and the general audience, and a factsheet for health professionals and other stakeholders. The project factsheet (Figure 15) and the first infographic are already published in our media kit, whereas the AI-Mind roll-up is available through accelCLOUD to all consortium members and was already used during the [3rd General Assembly organised in Oslo](#) (September, 2021). The materials will be translated into the languages of our partners whenever possible to increase outreach and understanding of the project on a national level, especially the assets used by clinical partners for the recruitment of participants to the AI-Mind study. In M1-M12, other materials were also developed by the consortium and more are planned throughout the following phases, as further explained in Section 6 about the implementation pathway.

Target group

healthcare system, patients’ advocacy, science community, industry, regulatory bodies, other (general public)

Needs addressed

information about the project, knowledge about risk factors, knowledge about MCI and dementia

KPIs

100 distributed per item/print
min. 100 downloads per item/digital

Intelligent digital tools for screening of brain connectivity and dementia risk estimation in people affected by mild cognitive impairment

Why is the AI-Mind project needed?

According to the World Health Organisation (WHO), dementia affects around 50 million people worldwide and this number is expected to double over the next 20 years. Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI), a condition intermediate between normal brain ageing and dementia, affects up to 18% of people age 60 or older. Up to 50% of people with MCI are at risk of progressing to dementia within 5 years*. With an ageing society, there is an urgent need for early risk assessment and intervention. The lack of screening tools prevents health professionals to identify the risk of developing dementia at an early stage of cognitive decline. We wish to introduce a new diagnostic opportunity of automatized, EEG-based, functional brain network analysis into the clinical world.

*Rossini, PM et al. "The Italian INCERPTOR Project", Journal of Alzheimer's Disease, vol. 72, no. 2, pp. 373-388, 2019, DOI: 10.3233/JAD-190670

What are the objectives?

The AI-Mind project will develop two **AI-based tools**, one for brain screening and another for dementia risk estimation. Both integrated into a **cloud-based platform** easily accessible to health professionals.

With this the AI-Mind project aims to:

- Improve healthcare systems through the use of AI.
- Deliver timely and reliable dementia risk estimation.
- Provide treatment effect evaluations before the onset of dementia.
- Increase the screening rate of MCI.
- Strengthen research & innovation capacity across Europe.

Key facts

Coordinator
Dr Ira Haraldsen
Oslo University Hospital, Norway
contact@ai-mind.eu

Duration
01.03.2021 - 28.02.2026

Budget
14 million euro

Programme
EU Horizon 2020 / Health Research & Innovation Action

Website
www.ai-mind.eu
@AI_Mind_EU

Consortium
15 partners, 8 countries

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 964220.

What is the concept?

In the heart of AI-Mind are two **AI-based tools** for brain area communication and dementia risk estimation, that analyse data in an innovative manner:

What will be the impact of the project?

The AI-Mind tools will significantly impact patients’ and doctors’ diagnostic journeys, reducing the currently lengthy process from several years to only one **week of investigation**.

AI-Mind partners

- Coordinator, Oslo University Hospital, NO
- Aalto University, FI
- accelpmentCH, CH
- Alzheimer Europe, LU
- BrainSymp AS, NO
- Det Norske Veritas Group, NO
- Helsinki University Hospital, FI
- Scientific Institute for Research, Hospitalisation and Healthcare, San Raffaele Pisana, IT
- Lurtis Rules S.L, ES
- Neuroconnect, IT
- Oslo Metropolitan University, NO
- Radboud University Medical Center, NL
- Tallinn University, EE
- Universidad Complutense Madrid, ES
- Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, IT

Figure 15 The first project factsheet available as part of the “media kit” on the AI-Mind website and shared with all consortium members.

5.1.7 Dementia prevention events

Target group

healthcare system,
patients' advocacy,
regulatory bodies,
other (general public)

Needs addressed

information about
the project,
knowledge about risk
factors,
knowledge about MCI
and dementia

KPIs

min. 4 events
50 people/event

The AI-Mind consortium will jointly organise four national dementia prevention events in the four European countries participating in the AI-Mind study (Norway, Finland, Italy and Spain) in collaboration with clinical sites. These events aim to inform the audience about the risk factors of dementia and how people can prevent them. AI-Mind wants to highlight the importance of early screening for dementia and emphasise awareness by raising and sharing knowledge. Clinical sites are best suited to organise these events, considering their well-established local networks and collaborations with relevant associations, such as [Federación de Alzheimer de la Comunidad de Madrid](#) (FAFAL) in Spain and the [Norwegian Pensioners' Association](#) in Norway, which support patient outreach. Although the format of the event, agenda and dates depend on site-specific capacities, the consortium will consider a harmonised approach when scheduling dementia prevention events. Nevertheless, it has been agreed to hold these between M19 and M48. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, organising events with vulnerable people may not be appropriate and for that reason, we have chosen the period when holding in-person events is more likely to be accepted. Doing so will ensure the highest and most direct impact on the target audiences. The clinical teams will also be responsible for contacting local specialists and sending invitations to research participants, informal carers, clinicians and doctors. AE will provide support by promoting these events to their national member organisation. As an organisation, AE also aims to incorporate an additional event as part of its annual AE conference to target a much broader audience, including people with MCI, informal carers, academics and the general public. AI-Mind will be involved in such an undertaking.

accleCH will provide support to clinical partners by developing communication materials that can be used during the events, including banners, programme templates, flyers and other assets that are deemed appropriate. Moreover, in due time, each event will be announced using AI-Mind Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter accounts. Messages and visuals used for this promotion will address different groups – notably, on Facebook, we will focus on people with MCI and informal carers; with the LinkedIn account, we will refer to health professionals and specialists; and Twitter will serve as a “news” platform to inform the general public about the events.

5.2 AI-Mind communicates about the study

The AI-Mind observational study is a key part of the project. The study will involve 1,000 participants with MCI, aged between 60 and 80, who are being recruited from five European centres located in Norway, Finland, Italy and Spain. Following Brolo’s SMCR model, we will tailor our communication not only with respect to the cognitive abilities of people with MCI but to the requirements of the local audiences immersed in different cultural contexts. It’s worth mentioning that patient recruitment continues to be a major challenge in clinical trials, with 19% of trials being terminated due to poor recruitment and another one-third needing to extend recruitment time.¹⁸

Figure 16 AI-Mind study takes place in Norway, Italy, Finland and Spain.

5.2.1 Local recruitment strategies

The AI-Mind clinical partners have developed local recruitment strategies, ensuring that these align with country-specific regulations. Moreover, the organisation of health systems differs from country to country, requiring that partners build on local networks and apply the most appropriate communication channels. The following sections how, who, to whom and the expected impact, present an overview of the planned communication activities provided by clinical sites.

5.2.1.1 Norway

How?

1. Multichannel approach

Through TV interviews on national television ([NRK](#)), radio interviews on national radio (NRK), news articles and magazine coverage in the following magazines [Utposten](#), [Slaqnytt](#), [Pensjonisten](#) and [Apollon](#).

2. Social media coverage

OUS aims to reach about 50,000 health professionals, clinicians and people with MCI via its Facebook and Instagram pages. Other professional Facebook groups will be used to disseminate AI-Mind project activities (e.g. Allmennlegeinitiativet with over 4,000 participants and MedHjelper).

Target group

healthcare system,
patients’ advocacy

Needs addressed

information about
the study,
knowledge about MCI
and dementia,
improved quality of life,
recommendations

KPIs

250 participants
recruited study location

3. Knowledge sharing

To expand knowledge about the AI-Mind project among different target groups in Norway, OUS will share presentations and lectures in its recruitment strategy. OUS will also send information emails to all memory clinics and dementia teams in each county. Also, to bring experts in dementia, pharmacology and AI together with patient organisations, health professionals will hold a two-day AI-Mind course, which will provide in-depth knowledge to improve clinical practice in primary care.

Who?

Associations: OUS, MEDHjelper, NRK, National Association for Heart and Lung Diseases ([LHL](#)), [Norwegian Pensioners' Association](#), [University of Oslo](#).

To whom?

People with MCI, clinicians, caregivers and the general public in the Oslo area.

What is the impact?

- Increased recruitment and awareness of the study
- With the multichannel approach, more than 200,000 people reached
- Around 3,000 health professionals

5.2.1.2 *Finland*

How?

1. Network

Around 100 participants will be recruited through the neurology clinic at Helsinki University Hospital (HUS) by screening patients who have received a diagnosis of MCI or experienced other signs of cognitive function decline and awareness during the previous year. The screening will be conducted by clinical neurologists working at the clinic. In addition, potential patient organisations may be involved in the recruitment process (via, e.g., Finnish memory disorder organisations).

2. Recruitment material

The recruitment will include other neurology clinics in the Helsinki metropolitan area, which serve around 1.5 million inhabitants. The neurologists will be provided with AI-Mind recruitment material, including study explanatory videos and study flyers.

3. Multichannel approach

Potential participants in the general public will be targeted by social media, webpages and newspaper advertising campaigns.

Who?

Clinical staff at HUS; potential participants contacted by phone. Health professionals and neurology clinics in the Helsinki area.

To whom?

People with MCI, clinicians, caregivers and the general public in the Helsinki area.

What is the impact?

- Raised awareness of the AI-Mind project among the target audiences.
- Ensure that around 100 potential participants can be recruited from the neurology clinic at HUH.
- Different channels of communication and tools will spread information about the project among the general public in the Helsinki area (around 600,000 inhabitants) and in the larger Helsinki metropolitan area (1.5 million inhabitants).

5.2.1.3 Spain

How?

1. Social media coverage

First, UCM plans to target potential participants through the websites of the universities and hospitals associated with the project. Additionally, posts presenting AI-Mind will be shared on different local media.

2. Recruitment material

The recruitment will be broadened to include relatives of MCI patients by distributing the study flyers. Different UCM facilities and centres will also have information points about the various projects that are currently involved in research studies, including AI-Mind.

3. Explanatory video

The study explanatory video will also be displayed in the waiting rooms of the neurology and gerontology units at Hospital Clínico San Carlos, associated with UCM (about 5,000 health professionals).

Who?

Associations: [Asociación de Familiares de Enfermos de Alzheimer de Madrid \(AFAL/AFADEMA\)](#), [Fundación Alzhéimer España](#), [Federación de Alzhéimer de la Comunidad de Madrid \(FAFAL\)](#), [Centro de prevención de deterioro cognitivo](#).

Clinicians in the collaborating hospitals and health professionals.

To whom?

People with MCI, clinicians, caregivers, associations and the general public in the Madrid area.

What is the impact?

- Raised awareness of the AI-Mind project among the target audiences.
- National associations are involved in outreach activities.
- Increased recruitment for the study.

5.2.1.4 Italy

UNIVERSITÀ
CATTOLICA
del Sacro Cuore

How?

1. Traditional media

The potential participants will be targeted through national TV broadcasting programmes, such as RAI1, RAI2 and RAI3. IRCCS will also achieve broader media coverage of the targeted audience through traditional media news, such as newspapers and online articles.

2. Multichannel approach

The digital platforms of San Raffaele are used to raise awareness of dementia and the AI-Mind project. Also, principal investigators from the clinical sites are guests on TV shows communicating about AI-Mind and the study. For instance, Prof. Paolo Maria Rossini gave an interview to the national news station RAI3 on Alzheimer's: the importance of prevention in October 2021.

3. Study material and network

The recruitment process will be expanded to general practitioners contacted with promotional and informative materials, including videos and flyers, distributed in the area of study clinics.

Who?

Principal investigators, communication offices at clinical sites, and general practitioners and clinicians within partner networks.

To whom?

People with MCI, clinicians, caregivers and the general public in the Rome area and Italy.

What is the impact?

- Raised awareness of the AI-Mind project among the target audiences.
- More than 250 participants were interested in the study and 250 enrolled.
- General practitioners have a broader overview of the AI-Mind project and contribute to the recruitment process.

5.2.2 Study materials – digital and print

The communication assets supporting recruitment were developed and provided to clinical partners by accelCH to guarantee their consistent style and are being used for recruitment. Moreover, to harmonise communication activities with the project timeline, we incorporated a tracking tool for the development of study-relevant materials and ensured that all helpful assets were available to clinical partners before enrolment in the AI-Mind study (Figure 17) started.

Target group	Needs addressed	Target groups:								
		Type	Material	Language	Format	Folded				
healthcare system, patients' advocacy	information about the study, knowledge about MCI and dementia, improved quality of life, recommendations	Print material	Flyer for GPs	EN	A5	No	✓		✓	
			Flyer for participants	EN	A5	F✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
			Poster about the study	EN	70x100 cm	No	✓	✓	✓	✓
		Website	Website content	EN/IT/NO/FN/SP	online	N.A.	✓	✓	✓	✓
		KPIs	500 visitors/ study page 200 views/ study video min. 100 flyers distributed/ print	Audio-visual	Explainer video	EN/IT/NO/FN/SP	online/ screens	N.A.	✓	✓
Events	Presentation at AE Conference			EN	online	N.A.	✓	✓	✓	✓
Other	Social media content			EN	online	N.A.	✓	✓	✓	✓
	News & articles			EN	online/ traditional	N.A.	✓	✓	✓	✓

Figure 17 AI-Mind study-relevant materials development tracking tool.

5.2.2.1 Digital – study pages on the AI-Mind website

AI-Mind study pages were developed in English for both target audiences: potential participants (Figure 18) and health professionals (Figure 19).

Study	Steps	Criteria	Local site	Testimonial	FAQ
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AI-Mind study takes place in Norway, Finland, Italy and Spain, and it aims to involve 1'000 participants.

The study will help to develop and validate artificial intelligence (AI) based tools to predict who is likely to develop dementia.

Mild cognitive impairment (MCI)

MCI is a condition in which the person experiences some memory loss, problems with concentration and/or thinking but maintains the ability to independently perform most activities of daily living. These symptoms are greater than in normal ageing. MCI is not the same as dementia, some people with MCI may develop dementia but others can revert back to normal cognitive functioning or remain stable over time.

Artificial Intelligence (AI)

AI refers to the performance by computer programs of tasks that are commonly associated with intelligent beings. The use of AI systems is becoming more common in healthcare (e.g. to support diagnosis or make predictions, recommendations or decisions). AI-Mind will use AI to develop models that mimic the functionality of human brain to better understand the MCI and create tools to predict people's risk of developing dementia.

Data protection

All the information collected from participants during the AI-Mind study will be kept confidential, securely encrypted and not used for purposes other than the AI-Mind project.

Watch our video about the study

[Read about our study](#)

Steps to follow

Go to the study page in your local language and contact the study team

Inform your doctor about the study and your interest in participation

Enroll in the AI-Mind study

Visit our clinical site 4 times over the next 2 years

What the visit would involve?

Interviews with the researchers

EEG and MEG tests (procedures to measure electrical activity in the brain)

Cognitive tests (tests of memory, thinking and language etc.)

A blood sample to understand genetic and other factors linked to the risk of developing dementia

Figure 18 AI-Mind study page (in English) addressing potential participants.

Are you interested in including your patients in the study? Register your interest at the **REGIONAL STUDY SITE** and we will contact you.

Study background

More than 10 million European show signs of mild cognitive impairment (MCI). The evolution of MCI differs from person to person, but many of those affected may progress to dementia. We know already that lifestyle changes and medical interventions can stop or slow down the development of dementia if the risk is identified at an early stage.

In the EU, the diagnosis of MCI is still largely based on classical neuropsychological testing (NTP). However, NTP is unable to discriminate within the MCI population between those who will progress to dementia and those who will not.

AI-Mind aims to establish an early population-based, cost-efficient screening method for synaptic pathology by empowering electroencephalogram (EEG) with a more sophisticated data interpretation and analysis.

Thanks to artificial intelligence (AI)-based tools, AI-Mind will offer health professionals the opportunity to apply preventive interventions for modifiable risk factors and initiate treatment early in the course of the disease.

Study facts

Part of international 5-years project

Enrolled in 4 countries in 5 hospitals

2 years duration

250 participants per country, 1000 participants in total

Secured data management

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- Men and women aged between 60 and 80 years
- MMSE>25 points, MOCA> 17 points, suggestive of MCI
- IADL/ADL / ADCS-ADL
- Petersen/Winblad criteria, 1.5 SD in one or more domains (will be evaluated by the AI-Mind team)
- CDR≤0.5

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- History of a major stroke, major neuropsychiatric disorder, severe head trauma, alcohol abuse, malignancy within 5 years
- Recent initialization of psychotropic drugs including AChEI and Memantine

Figure 19 AI-Mind study page addressing health professionals.

Additionally, based on the assumption that the knowledge of English (a factor influencing communication in view of the SMCR model) among people aged 65+ isn't sufficient to decode AI-Mind messages, we prepared other language versions for the "study" page addressing potential participants.

For each country in which the AI-Mind study will take place, we developed a dedicated sub-page. [Norwegian](#), [Italian](#), [Finnish](#) and [Spanish](#) sub-pages can easily be reached in one click through the drop-down menu or via the box with the flag of the respective country on the homepage (Figure 20). This will increase outreach at the local level, while the possibility of contacting the local study team either with the email address provided or via contact form on the page will facilitate enrolment in the study.

What is the challenge?

There are over 50 million people worldwide living with dementia and by 2030 this number is expected to reach 82 million.

The ageing brain becomes vulnerable to decline and keeping independency in daily life can become a challenge for the elderly. People with Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI), an intermediate condition between normal brain ageing and dementia, may develop dementia in the future.

There is an urgent need for early risk assessment and intervention. Current practices with time-consuming patient investigations focus on late symptoms management due to a lack of diagnostic tools. This causes numerous implications in terms of familial, medical and care costs.

Latest News

The AI-Mind study has kicked

Tweets

Figure 20 AI-Mind home page and boxes redirecting to the study pages in the local language.

5.2.2.2 Digital – study explanatory video

To support recruitment to the AI-Mind study and inform potential participants what the research consists of, the [explanatory video](#) (Figure 21) was developed within the first year of the project duration. An original script was produced according to the project objectives to ensure that it met the needs of the target audience. The main character, Mary, is in her sixties and works in administration. Being recently diagnosed with MCI, she looks for the opportunity to contribute to the research regarding this condition and information on what such a study may look like. When finding a European initiative, the AI-Mind project, Mary joins the study and visits the local study site four times over two years.

accelCH, with input from clinical partners and support of AE, produced an animated video first in English and then in [Norwegian](#), [Finnish](#), [Italian](#) and [Spanish](#) to increase the impact at the national level. Each language version of the video is embedded on the “local study page”, is available on [YouTube](#) and has been shared with clinical partners for them to use in their recruitment activities.

Figure 21 Scenes from the AI-Mind study explanatory video.

5.2.2.3 Print – study flyer and poster

Two versions of the flyer, **A5 two-sided** (for less information) and **A5 folded** (for more information), as shown in Figure 22, were developed to support clinical partners in their recruitment activities. Depending on the preference, clinical partners can use both. The content for the flyer was discussed with AE, which has a wide experience of engaging in communication with people with dementia and, due to their involvement in other European projects, was able to provide helpful input to the design. The flyers were prepared in English with a sample text that served as a “place holder” not to be used by local teams. Each clinical partner will use a version that is tailored to the local audience in terms of content (text) and language.

Concerned about your memory?

We are looking for participants to the European research study for dementia prevention.

The study may be for you if you:

- are aged between 60 and 75
- have been diagnosed with mild cognitive impairment or/and experience significant memory, thinking or concentration problems
- do not have dementia or any other condition that is causing your memory problem
- want to contribute to the validation of tools for better dementia prediction
- are willing to take part in regular study assessments

ai-mind.eu

What is the AI-Mind study about?

The AI-Mind study will examine the brain connectivity of people with MCI and will collect data to build and validate AI-Mind tools. We will use artificial intelligence (AI) to develop models to understand and predict who is likely to develop dementia.

Local study:

Oslo universitetssykehus
Oslo universitetssykehus
Bygg 34 ved Ullevål Sykehus,
N-0450 Oslo

Contact information:

Cathrine Faye
+47 22 11 85 92

Vebjørn Andersson
+47 23 01 62 59

catfay@ous-hf.no

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 964220
The contents of this flyer are the sole responsibility of (name of the implementing partner) and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union.

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In cosa consiste lo studio AI-Mind?

Lo studio AI-Mind esaminerà la connettività cerebrale di persone con MCI e raccoglierà i dati allo scopo di costruire e validare strumenti diagnostici di Intelligenza Artificiale (AI). Utilizzeremo modelli di AI per comprendere e predire lo sviluppo di una eventuale demenza.

Come funziona?

Lo studio riguarderà 1000 partecipanti con MCI, di età compresa tra 60 e 80 anni che saranno reclutati in 5 paesi europei: Norvegia, Finlandia, Italia e Spagna. I partecipanti saranno chiamati a presentarsi nel centro di riferimento quattro volte nel corso di due anni.

In cosa consiste la visita?

- Una breve intervista con il nostro staff clinico.
- Durante la prima visita ti sarà richiesto di effettuare un prelievo di sangue in modo da poter eseguire i test genetici.
- Sarà condotta una registrazione elettroencefalografica (EEG) con equipaggiamento all'avanguardia per misurare l'attività cerebrale.
- Verranno condotti test su memoria, ragionamento e linguaggio.
- I dati, incluso l'esame neuropsicologico, verranno raccolti durante le visite di controllo.

Lo studio potrebbe essere giusto per te se:

- Hai tra i 60 e gli 80 anni
- Pensi di avere problemi significativi di memoria, ragionamento o concentrazione
- Vuoi contribuire alla validazione di strumenti per una miglior predizione della demenza
- Sei disposto a prendere parte alle valutazioni di uno studio di ricerca
- Sei disposto a recarti presso il sito a te più vicino (l'indirizzo è sul retro di questo volantino)

Se sei interessato a partecipare allo studio o se ti piacerebbe soltanto avere informazioni, per favore non esitare ammetterti in contatto con il team AI-Mind. Puoi trovare i nostri contatti qui in fondo e troverai più informazioni sul retro di questo volantino.

Contatta il team AI-Mind per partecipare

Tel 06 5225 2326

Mail info.aimindproject@gmail.com

Figure 22 Two-sided AI-Mind study flyer in English (top) and the inside of the folded flyer in Italian (bottom).

5.3 AI-Mind and community of people with dementia

The wider dementia community (i.e. Alzheimer’s associations, research participants, patient groups, carers) is a key audience of the AI-Mind project and special attention is paid to transforming their interest into involvement. By becoming advocates of the AI-Mind, these groups will raise further awareness about the project, the need for timely diagnosis and prevention, the AI-Mind study and the aims of our research. The consortium will reach these groups in two ways: first, by involving national associations in outreach activities performed by clinical partners, and second, by building an umbrella for AI-Mind engagement with a community of people with dementia, based on the expertise of one AI-Mind partner. AE will use its extensive network of 37 member associations from 33 countries and its cross-channel, multitool communication approach to provide regular updates on the AI-Mind project, as shown below.

- **Newsletter:** AE circulates its newsletter on a monthly basis to a large audience, reaching around 11,000 people. A dedicated section on EU projects provides updates on EU projects in which AE is involved. In 2021, 10 articles about the AI-Mind project were included in this section. Additional articles will be published over the next few years.
- **Website:** All AI-Mind articles published in the AE Newsletter will also be featured on the AE website.
- **Social media channels:** Communications **shared** through the AI-Mind social media channels will also be supported through the AE channels, including Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn.
- **Dementia in Europe magazine:** AE releases its *Dementia in Europe* magazine three times per year. The magazine is distributed to all members of the European Parliament and to many high-level decision makers in the EC. It also reaches lawmakers, politicians, research professionals from public and private bodies and scientific partners who work together with AE on various projects. The AI-Mind project was [featured in an interview with project leader Ira Haraldsen \(OUS\) in June 2021](#). Additional articles will be included in future editions.
- **Annual conferences:** AI-Mind will be able to participate each year in the AE annual conference, which attracts over 500 attendees, including patients, carers, policymakers, health and social care professionals and researchers. The participation of the AI-Mind project in this conference will represent another opportunity to share the progress of the project and disseminate its results. The AI-Mind project was presented in December 2021 at the [31st Alzheimer Europe Annual Conference](#). AI Mind had an exhibition space dedicated to the project, with various resources, including a project factsheet and infographics available for download. The recording of the presentation given by the project coordinator on “[Artificial intelligence as key for dementia prevention for people affected by mild cognitive impairment](#)” is also available on YouTube. The event welcomed 600 online participants.

The above communication means provide an opportunity to target Alzheimer’s associations/patient groups and policymakers affiliated with AE as well as the general public and civil society.

Target group

regulatory bodies,
patients’ advocacy,
other (general public)

Needs addressed

information about
the project,
knowledge about MCI
and dementia,
improved quality of life,
recommendations

KPIs

Newsletter: 500
downloads

Website: approx. 500
visitors per month

Social media:
500 followers /channel
80 posts/channel
20 shares /comments
/likes per post/tweet

Dementia in Europe
magazine: 2,500 issues
distributed in print and
digital

AE annual conference:
600
participants/conference

5.4 AI-Mind disseminates project results

5.4.1 Dissemination platforms

Target group

healthcare system, science community, industry, regulatory bodies

Needs addressed

new knowledge, advancement in science, use of the project's results, recommendations and guidelines, information about the project results and applicability of methods in other research

KPIs

GDO KE Platform: min. 1 resource accepted

Research Gate: min. 20 reads/publication

Open Research: min. 3 uses of shared data

5.4.1.1 Global Dementia Observatory Knowledge Exchange

The consortium will explore all opportunities to contribute its resources, e.g. booklets, courses and toolkits, to the [Global Dementia Observatory \(GDO\) Knowledge Exchange \(KE\) Platform](#). Such materials will be submitted to the GDO

World Health Organization

KE Platform to go through a comprehensive review process consisting of a panel of peer reviewers, including experts in the field of dementia, a focus group of people with lived experience of dementia and the WHO secretariat. This online platform from WHO aims to facilitate the exchange of information and knowledge on dementia. The GDO KE Platform contains key resources to support the implementation of the [Global action plan on the public health response to dementia 2017-2025](#) and its seven action areas and enhance countries' and communities' responses to dementia by providing a space to share resources (e.g. policies, guidelines, case studies and examples of good practice) at no cost.

5.4.1.2 ResearchGate

All AI-Mind publications will be shared on the project's website through a section dedicated to the project's results. To amplify the dissemination outreach and engage the scientific community, an [AI-Mind profile page](#) has been created on the networking platform **ResearchGate**. This page will be used as a repository of scientific AI-Mind publications and will be updated on a regular basis. Furthermore, collaborating partners will be included and will be able to share AI-Mind papers. Followers of the AI-Mind project profile will be informed about any updates on this page, resulting in wider dissemination outreach and visibility of the project's results. ResearchGate is a social networking site for scientists and researchers which allows them to share papers, ask and answer questions, and find potential collaborators. It is a large academic social network in terms of active users.

5.4.1.3 Open research data

It is envisaged that AI-Mind clinical data will be shared to EU platforms such as [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#) and/or [EBRAINS](#). The latter intends to secure Europe's digital leadership, underpinned by advances in the development of brain-inspired AI, neurorobotics and neuromorphic computing systems. EBRAINS data sets – to support continuous advancement of the field – are drawn from multiple sources within and externally to the [Human Brain Project](#), and are curated to offer FAIR characteristics, accessible through EBRAINS Knowledge Graph services. From the identification of relevant data, the Knowledge Graph provides a multimodal metadata store, the linkage between experimental and neuroscientific data and a connection to software and hardware tools for analysis.

Whether and how this can be achieved within AI-Mind will require further study of GDPR and national laws, as well as close alignment and agreements between AI-Mind partners, their data protection officers and legal support. Further discussions within the AI-Mind consortium will be required to ensure that the utility and sustainability of health data collected within AI-Mind can be achieved.

KPIs

Zenodo: 49 public deliverables available

Dementia in Europe: 2,500 issues distributed in print and digital form

5.4.1.4 Zenodo

It is envisaged that AI-Mind data, namely scientific publications and public deliverables, will be uploaded to EU platforms such as [Zenodo](#). This free open-access repository is a result of the [OpenAIRE project](#) in collaboration with [CERN](#). This repository is in line with the FAIR principles since it eliminates barriers to adopting data-sharing practices. Data is **findable** via a digital object identifier (DOI), which is attributed to every output (from journal articles to patents, conference papers, datasets, figures, etc.) uploaded. It allows **accessibility**, since we can define the access rights to the output, such as Open Access or Embargoed Access. As Zenodo is integrated into reporting for research funded by the EC via OpenAIRE, the funding agency will be automatically notified when the output from AI-Mind is uploaded. Furthermore, it's possible to associate the project output with a community such as the [Human Brain Project](#) (subject to approval). Zenodo uses [JSON Schema](#) as an internal representation of metadata and offers exports to other popular formats, such as [Dublin Core](#) or [MARCXML](#), which allows data to be **interoperable**. Since Zenodo offers the possibility of defining the respective Creative Commons copyright license, we can guarantee that the data are **reusable**. At the moment, one public deliverable has been approved by the EC: D7.1: Website establishment and focus group organisation. Therefore, this document has been [uploaded to Zenodo](#) and fully open access has been provided to it.

5.4.1.5 "Dementia in Europe" special issue from AI-Mind

AE, in collaboration with all consortium partners, will publish a special supplement on AI-Mind in their *Dementia in Europe* magazine. This special issue (around 15-20 pages) will be published during the third fourth of the AI-Mind communication and dissemination strategy to facilitate the uptake of the project's results. The supplement will be printed and distributed to policymakers, advocacy groups, healthcare providers, research professionals from public and private bodies and scientific partners who work with AE on various projects. The supplement will also be available online for download. AE is planning to coincide the release of this supplement with the AI-Mind symposium at its annual conference. The supplement will be distributed to all attendees in their conference bags and will focus on the AI-Mind goals, structure, results, benefits of early screening and intervention of dementia, MCI and the need for change in clinical practice. It will also include interviews with AI-Mind WP leaders.

5.4.2 AI-Mind events – knowledge sharing

5.4.2.1 Webinar series

AI-Mind will provide a series of webinars throughout the project **on three levels:**

- Organised collectively by WPs or the AI-Mind consortium, these will focus on methods applied in the project, the AI-Mind results and benefits for the patients arising from the AI-Mind technology. Two webinars from WP2, open to the public, were organised in the first year of the project duration and recordings from both, [Neurophysiological basis of EEG and MEG signals](#) and [Fundamentals of source reconstruction on EEG and MEG](#), are available on YouTube.

All AI-Mind partners will ensure that webinars open to the public raise no confidential issues and will inform the consortium in due time about the scope of the disseminated information. accelCH will support promoting these events via the AI-Mind website and social media, and consortium members will further announce events within their networks. Promotion of webinars will be done in collaboration with partners organising the event and will be announced at least five weeks in advance of the date.

All webinars will be recorded and made available on YouTube and the AI-Mind website within Knowledge Hub (Section 5.5) to further disseminate the knowledge and ensure the sustainability of the material.

- Organised by consortium members according to their expertise and ones provided by AI-Mind collaborators, such as EBRAINS, to the AI-Mind network.

DNV, with vast experience in providing webinars to a broad range of audiences, will organise webinars on medical devices, their development and compliance with AI medical device software and on data governance and management, including one on Managing AI/ML data for development projects in health research. These will be open to the external audience.

In cooperation with the Norwegian Medical Association, **OUS** will develop and organise a two-day course for general practitioners on how to ensure timely MCI diagnosis and improve screening methods. This course is part of the AI-Mind events series that aims at providing knowledge in areas such as MCI and dementia, the use of AI in healthcare, EEG and MEG screening methods and risk factors.

- Building on new collaborations, such as one with EBRAINS, AI-Mind consortium members will benefit from webinars provided by EBRAINS on the research infrastructure.

Target group

healthcare system, science community, industry, regulatory bodies

Needs addressed

scientific collaboration, new knowledge, information about the project results and applicability of methods in other research, recommendations and guidelines

KPIs

Webinars: 20 participants/event

5.4.2.2 Twitter conference

The AI-Mind Twitter conference was planned due to its successful implementation by AALTO at the [BrainTC Twitter Conference](#) (2017-2019) which then became [OHBMx](#) in 2020 with the organisation for human brain mapping from NeuroImage editors. It was envisioned that such a conference would ensure broad outreach and dissemination of the AI-Mind results. However, during the development of the CDP and knowledge sharing session with organisers of the original #BrainTC from AALTO, decreased interest in such an event has been reported, which is assumed to be the result of two main factors: the increasing number of Twitter and other social media conferences or seminars amid various disciplines and the COVID-19 pandemic. It has become clear that the “novelty factor” that ensured the success of the first events is no longer applicable. Several research studies have indicated the problem with increasing screen time during the COVID-19 pandemic that has negative impacts on physical and mental health.¹⁹ With long times in front of screens, people have become more critical to the way they interact online and reach towards “offline” time whenever possible to balance daily “screen time”. Based on the experience and lessons learned from OHMBx, it seems appropriate to adapt the initial idea to the current situation to ensure the best ratio efforts/impact. The consortium will explore other possibilities for disseminating AI-Mind results and sharing knowledge with the general audience. For example, it’s envisioned that talks and presentations from General Assemblies of the consortium or symposia could be streamlined through AI-Mind social media accounts. Another opportunity for community building could be organisation Q&A sessions, where AI-Mind experts will present results and interact with the public within a given time by answering questions from the audience.

5.4.2.3 AI-Mind session at the AE Conference

AI-Mind will hold a symposium at the annual AE conference. This session will last 1-2 hours and will include oral presentations by various AI-Mind partners. Attendees will be able to ask questions of some of the lead researchers involved in the project. This symposium will be organised in the fourth phase of the AI-Mind communication and dissemination strategy to disseminate the project’s results. This symposium will constitute a key action in our dissemination strategy to make an impact on the dementia community by using the extensive network of AE.

During this symposium, presentations on the project activities and outcomes will be delivered to an audience of people living with dementia, healthcare professionals, representatives from AE’s member organisations, policymakers, academic researchers, representatives of industry, payers, regulators and HTA bodies. Presentations may include the demonstration of AI-Mind tools and the presentation of explorative pathways. The event will be announced through AI-Mind and AE communication channels and supported via partner channels. Graphics will be created and shared via social media channels to provide maximum exposure.

5.4.2.4 AI-Mind at the European Parliament

As a European umbrella organisation that brings together 37 national Alzheimer’s associations across 33 countries, AE has a well-established policy network. AE liaises with European and national policymakers through the [European Alzheimer’s Alliance](#) of Members of the European Parliament (composed of almost 100 members) with an

KPIs

AE conference: 600 participants

European Parliament session: 100 participants

interest in dementia, its involvement in the [2nd EU Joint Action on Dementia](#) and its participation in the Group of Governmental Experts on Dementia.

To disseminate AI-Mind project results to policymakers at the EU level, AE will organise a session during one of their European Parliament Lunch Debates in Brussels (Belgium), where AI-Mind partners will present the research results and highlight the importance of early screening for dementia. Three speakers will give oral presentations and hold Q&A sessions with attendees. It has been agreed that this event will be held in the third or fourth phase of the AI-Mind DISCO strategy because this period will be more appropriate for holding in-person events. In person format will ensure the highest and most direct impact on the target audiences. AE regularly organises these meetings, which are chaired by a member of the European Parliament and provide an opportunity to bring science closer to policymakers. People in attendance are EU policymakers, national health ministries, representatives from national Alzheimer’s associations, pharmaceutical companies, researchers and members of the European Working Group of People with Dementia.

5.4.3 International conferences

Participation in conferences will constitute a key action in our dissemination strategy to make an impact on the scientific community. The AI-Mind consortium members have extensive knowledge of scientific, industry and policy events at the European, national and local levels covering dementia, Alzheimer’s disease, AI, neurodegenerative diseases, neuroimaging and big data. The AI-Mind researchers are committed to participating in external events, including conferences, digital exhibitions, international forums and scientific symposia, to showcase the project results. All partners will be encouraged through internal communication channels to regularly attend the most important conferences worldwide and every opportunity will be taken to present the AI-Mind project and its results, either in the form of oral communications or posters. A list of international conferences where the project could be presented will be developed and it will be continuously updated with new items that the researchers will identify. This list of meetings and events will be made available to consortium members through the internal accelCLOUD platform, where partners will be able to directly add relevant conferences.

Moreover, a “Dissemination opportunities” file has been developed as a base for the abovementioned list, including other relevant events next to international conferences, such as workshops or webinars (Annex 5). The file is available on an internal platform and the events are included in the “Events calendar” on the AI-Mind website.

Conferences of interest include the Alzheimer’s Association International Conference, the Alzheimer’s Disease & Parkinson Disease (AD/PD) International Conference, Advances in Alzheimer Therapy (AAT) and AD/PD™, the AE Conference, the Professional Society for Health Economics and Outcomes Research (ISPOR) Annual Conference, Health Technology Assessment International, and the Global AI Festival.

Target group

healthcare system, science community, industry, regulatory bodies

Needs addressed

scientific collaboration, new knowledge, information about the project results and applicability of methods in other research, recommendations and guidelines, business opportunities, strengthened R&I capacity

KPIs

30 presentations

5.4.4 Peer-reviewed open access publications

Target group

healthcare system,
science community,
industry, regulatory
bodies

Needs addressed

new knowledge,
information about the
project results and
applicability of
methods in
other research,
recommendations and
guidelines

KPIs

min. 30 high impact
publications

AI-Mind partners are encouraged to publish their research results in peer-reviewed, high-impact journals and other publication outlets. We identified the seven journals most relevant for the project’s scientific publications as described below.

A full list of publication outlets that may be of interest to partners is under development and will be available to all consortium members through the internal platform by M19 of the project. To cover intersectoral dimensions of the AI-Mind project, the list will include publication channels from AI, ethics, neurosciences and data governance. The first version is attached as Annex 4 to this deliverable.

In line with Horizon 2020 participation rules, all peer-reviewed journal articles will be openly accessible and free of charge through either gold or green open access (see Section 3.4.2).

accelCH has developed a self-monitoring tool, the accelDISCO CONSOLE, and made it available to all partners through accelCLOUD. It is based on the Continuous Reporting online form within the Funding & Tenders Portal. Easy access to all AI-Mind partners facilitates the collection of activities, including their outreach and impact range. A list of publications produced by the AI-Mind consortium will be updated within this tool, as shown in Figure 23.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
	DOI	Type of scientific publication	Repository Link	Title	Authors	Title of the Journal/Proceedings/Books series/Book (for book chapters)	Number, date or frequency of the Journal/Proceedings/Book	Relevant Pages	ISBN	Publisher	Place of publication	Date of submission to publishing body
1												
2												
3												
4												
5												
6												
7												
8												

Figure 23 Communication and dissemination tracking tool available to all AI-Mind partners on the internal platform.

Journal: *European Journal of Neuroscience (EJN)*

Description: Biweekly peer-reviewed scientific journal covering all aspects of neuroscience. It is the official journal of FENS. Available in free access to all FENS members, it publishes papers on a broad range of topics aiming to advance our understanding of the nervous system in health and disease.

Impact factor: 3.386

Journal: *Alzheimer's & Dementia*

Description: *Journal of the Alzheimer's Association* aims to bridge the knowledge gaps across a wide range of bench-to-bedside investigations. The journal publishes the results of studies in behaviour, biochemistry, genetics, molecular biology, pharmacology, physiology, protein chemistry, neurology, neuropathology, psychiatry, geriatrics, neuropsychology, epidemiology, sociology, health services research, health economics, political science and public policy.

Impact factor: 21.566

Journal: *EU Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*

Description: This journal facilitates progress in understanding the etiology, pathogenesis, epidemiology, genetics, behaviour, treatment and psychology of Alzheimer's disease. The journal publishes research reports, reviews, short communications, book reviews and letters-to-the-editor. The journal is dedicated to providing an open forum for original research that will expedite our fundamental understanding of Alzheimer's disease.

Impact factor: 4.472

Journal: *Annals of Neurology*

Description: This journal publishes articles of broad interest with potential for high impact in understanding the

mechanisms and treatment of diseases of the human nervous system. All areas of clinical and basic neuroscience, including new technologies, cellular and molecular neurobiology, population sciences, and studies of behaviour, addiction and psychiatric diseases, are of interest to the journal.

Impact factor: 10.42

Journal: *Journal of Neurology*

Description: International peer-reviewed English-language journal which publishes on all aspects of clinical neurology from diagnosis to treatment. Founded in 1891, the *Journal of Neurology* has reliably published excellent research in neurology for over 130 years. The journal publishes original communications, reviews, commentaries, letters to the editor and pioneers in neurology, as well as the invited neurological updates and journal clubs.

Impact factor: 4.849

Journal: *BRAIN*

Description: This peer-reviewed scientific journal of neurology was founded in 1878 by John Charles Bucknill, David Ferrier, James Crichton-Browne and John Hughlings Jackson. It is published by Oxford University Press.

Impact factor: 13.501

Journal: *PloS ONE*

Description: A peer-reviewed open access scientific journal published by the Public Library of Science (PLOS) since 2006. The journal covers primary research from any discipline within science and medicine.

Impact factor: 4.411

5.5 AI-Mind Knowledge Hub

The first dimension of RRI highlighted by the EC – multi-actor and public engagement (PE) – is about co-creating the response to societal challenges by bringing together the diversity of actors, including researchers and innovators, SME, policymakers, nongovernmental organisations, civil society associations and citizens. With this in mind, we will create a dedicated space on the AI-Mind website that invites all key target groups to benefit from the provided information. Through the AI-Mind Knowledge Hub, we will diffuse knowledge on five levels.

- A dedicated area, “**Brain Collection**”, will be included to introduce existing schemes for dementia prevention and intervention. The space will incorporate related news from outside the project and work as a hub for all people interested in dementia intervention.
- A network of PhD students and young researchers involved in the AI-Mind project, **PhD & Young Researcher Club**, will be developed and strengthened through the AI-Mind educational programme. An overview of online courses offered by AI-Mind partnering institutions and supporting organisations such as [NORA](#) and [CALIRE](#) will be available under a dedicated section. One of NORA’s objectives is to organise relevant forums to promote research and education in AI through [NORA.Research.School](#). AI-Mind will benefit from this collaboration by not only including courses and workshops offered by NORA on the AI-Mind Knowledge Hub but also supporting early-stage researchers and PhD students involved in the project to take these courses as part of their educational programme. Further impact will be generated by offering the possibility to register for some of the listed courses by researchers outside the AI-Mind consortium.
- All materials developed by the AI-Mind consortium and its members’ webinars will be available through the Knowledge Hub, including materials from lecturers for general practitioners on how to improve and initiate high-quality MCI diagnostics.
- Report on best clinical practice guidelines developed as part of deliverable 1.6, including an analysis of the socio-ethical, technical and clinical aspects of the AI-Mind diagnostics tools implementation in a clinical setting.
- **AI-Mind Educational Toolboxes** that are part of the guidelines for clinicians and other healthcare providers in detail are described in deliverable *User guidelines for clinicians and scientific dissemination* (D7.3) as well as Starter Kit (Section 5.4.6.1), which will be finalised in M60 and reported as a deliverable 7.7.

Target group

healthcare system, patients’ advocacy, science community, industry, regulatory bodies

Needs addressed

scientific collaboration, new knowledge, information about the project results and applicability of methods in other research, recommendations and guidelines, knowledge about MCI, dementia and risks factors

KPIs

Brain Collection: min. 20 resources

PhD & Young Researcher Club: min. 3 sessions yearly, min 10 developed resources available, min. 5 online courses listed

Educational Toolboxes: min. 10 toolboxes developed

Figure 24 AI-Mind Knowledge Hub foreseen input and generated impact.

5.6 AI-Mind tools – the AI-Mind Connector and Predictor

5.6.1 AI-Mind starter kit

Target group

healthcare system,
science community,
industry, regulatory
bodies

Needs addressed

scientific collaboration,
recommendations and
guidelines, business
opportunities,
digitalisation and
technological progress,
knowledge on the risks
factors and dementia
prevention

KPIs

Starter kit: 50
downloads

Demonstrators: 20
participants/ clinical
site

The starter kit will be developed as of M8 throughout the project lifecycle within Task 7.3, with the involvement of all partners and the lead of HUH. The aim of this task is to create the best approach to use and support clinical decisions based on the outcomes of the AI-Mind services when communicating with patients, particularly those with a predictive diagnosis of dementia. The starter kit will give future users of the AI-Mind Connector and AI-Mind Predictor the necessary knowledge and skills to deploy and utilise the AI-Mind technology. The development of the starter kit will follow a two-step approach. The first step involves creating the initial set of guidelines for internal use by AI-Mind-associated health professionals on all five sites. This kit will contain videos, guidelines in digital or print form and training workshops about the project's clinical study. A dedicated deliverable (D7.3) explaining the process in detail will be produced by the end of M12. BrainSymph, Neuroconnect and Lurtis will instrument early access to AI-Mind Connector and AI-Mind Predictor to collect the required information from beta testers in the following months. Step two will involve the development of the final starter kit for future users of the AI-Mind tools, notably clinicians, general physicians and other health providers. *User starter kit and guidelines for clinicians and hospitals* (D7.7) will consider the feedback from the beta testers at clinical sites and other stakeholders participating in the training or accessing produced materials through various AI-Mind channels from M12 to M60. The collected information will be reviewed and included in the produced documentation describing the uses and limitations of the AI-Mind tools. An instruction manual will be made accessible to interested clinics.

It's envisioned that the final starter kit will contain the following elements:

- Videos for specific procedures for data collection
- Guidelines and user manuals in printed format
- Flowcharts and other illustrated elements
- A web-based training area

Elements of the starter kit that don't bridge any confidentiality issues, following FAIR principles, will be made easily accessible through the AI-Mind Knowledge Hub and other platforms.

5.6.2 Demonstrators

Next to the development of the starter kit, the consortium will organise training at each of the AI-Mind pilot sites in Norway, Spain, Finland and Italy for local clinicians, such as general physicians, neurologists and healthcare providers. These clinicians will be able to experience the AI-Mind Predictor that is employed in the field as it would be applied in everyday practice. The training will also include education on the benefits of early intervention for dementia and the importance of implementing screening for MCI into the routine assessment of cognitive functions.

6 What is our implementation plan?

The lifecycle of AI-Mind has been planned as a sixty-month pathway, from March 2021 to its completion in February 2026. As various analyses showed, notably AI-Mind solution SWOT assessment and stakeholder identification, during this time the requirements of both the project and its stakeholders will change. To ensure that the different communication and dissemination objectives are achieved and that the shifting expectations of the target groups are efficiently addressed, AI-Mind plans its DISCO activities as a four-phase implementation approach.

One of the undoubted strengths of AI-Mind is the commitment of consortium members to ensuring the broad outreach of the project through active involvement in actions. Led by accelCH, WP7 will maximise the impact of AI-Mind by facilitating communication about the project and disseminating its results.

Furthermore, for each DISCO activity, responsibilities were assigned based on AI-Mind partners' fields, networks, outreach ranges and interests and are included in Annex 5.

**Dr Signe Daugbjerg
(UCSC)**
Lead of the Health
Technology Assessment
for the AI-Mind
Connector and

We make a holistic assessment on different parameters to assist the policymakers in deciding whether to implement the AI-Mind solution in clinical practice. I'm very excited to be a part of the project.

Planning & Initiation

Implementation & Monitoring

Closing

6.1 Implementation pathway

The outreach activities of AI-Mind were smoothly initiated at the start of the project. Overall, all of the activities included in “Description of Actions” (DoA) for the first year, as well as additional activities, have been completed successfully. Actions taken between M1 and M12 of the project have focused on raising awareness about the project and the AI-Mind study through cross-channel and multimedia approaches and stakeholder orientation. The implementation of outreach activities, which started in the “Planning & Initiation” phase will continue in the second and third “Implementation & Monitoring” phases. In these phases, the execution of actions will be more strategic, owing to the developed DISCO plan. Moreover, after M30, an internal evaluation of DISCO activities and the role of WP7 will be performed by the AI-Mind communication team to adapt further implementation of DISCO activities in the fourth and final “Closing” phase.

Planning & Initiation

- The DISCO plan development
- Define corporate design
- Setting up DISCO channels
- Defining DISCO tools
- Support study communication

Aims:

- Set up DISCO framework
- Raise awareness about the study and the project

Implementation & Monitoring

- The DISCO plan execution
- Implementation of communication activities
- Implementation of dissemination activities
- Continuous monitoring and performance evaluation based on KPIs
- Tracking DISCO activities

Aims:

- Raise awareness about the project
- Inform stakeholders about the activities and results
- Diffuse knowledge

Closing

- The DISCO plan execution assessment and adoption
- Implementation “closing activities”
- DISCO activities final control
- Summarising of the project results
- Follow-up opportunities

Aims:

- Disseminate project results
- Inform stakeholders about the achievements and the AI-Mind solution

Figure 25 The DISCO activities implementation pathway is divided into four phases with changing key aims and focus.

6.2 Implementation of communication activities

To better engage with the public and increase the impact, various outreach activities are planned as ongoing throughout the project lifecycle and beyond, including the project website, content material or explanatory videos. In Table 4 we present area-specific tactics for the respective phases that the AI-Mind consortium will establish to facilitate the implementation of particular communication activities.

Table 4 Tactics for specific areas and phases of communication strategy.

Communication Area	M1-M12	M13-M48	M49-M60
Project website	Design and develop the main project communication platform, complemented with analytics and search engine optimisation.	Obtain regular updates of the platform and track the analytics to measure the impact. Perform the first restructure of the website, including the development of the AI-Mind Knowledge Hub.	Obtain regular updates of the platform and track the analytics to measure the impact. Perform the second restructure, including the production of material regarding AI-Mind results.
Social media presence	Establish presence in social media, where the project reproduces relevant content and monitors relevant hashtags and uploads material. Include social media in local recruitment strategies for the AI-Mind study.	Promote the project's outcomes and events, interact with the relevant community, upload relevant material, reproduce relevant content. Regularly track the analytics to measure the impact.	Obtain continuous updates on the communication contents with the results of the study, produce infographics and include "closing campaign". Regularly track the analytics to measure the impact.
Online publishing and traditional media	Publish two press releases, online articles, interviews in television and local print media from AI-Mind partners.	Publish a press release announcing the project results. Ensure regular communication about advancements.	Partners communicate about the results on a national level. Press release
Communication materials (application specific)	Develop corporate materials and manuals for the consortium. Produce print material, including project factsheet, 1 st infographic, banner and study material. Develop 1 st explanatory video.	Update project factsheet, banner and visual material. Produce 2 nd flyer.	Develop final communication material for the AI-Mind outcomes, including a project factsheet, infographics, informative material for people with MCI and health professionals.
AI-Mind and community of people with dementia	Regular news in AE monthly Newsletter. Produce featured article for <i>Alzheimer in Europe</i> magazine. Present at the AE Annual Conference.	Organise four AI-Mind dementia events. Announce through AE channels. Develop supportive material.	Prepare a dedicated section for AI-Mind symposium at the AE Annual Conference.

Numerous activities have already been implemented by the AI-Mind consortium during the first 12 months of the project duration. These include

- launching the project website (D7.1),
- holding webinars,
- publishing press releases and news articles,
- setting up social media accounts with posts and videos, and
- producing print and digital materials; an overview of the produced and planned material is shown in Figure 26.

Figure 26 Produced in the first year of the project and planned AI-Mind materials including implementation time in project months.

6.3 Implementation of dissemination activities

Employing the same method for the implementation of dissemination of activities, AI-Mind partners will establish area-specific tactics for the respective phases. This aims to establish fundamentals for the specific activities described in Section 5 and to facilitate their implementation.

Table 5 Tactics for specific areas and phases of dissemination strategy.

Dissemination Area	M1-M12	M13-M48	M49-M60
AI-Mind resources and deliverables	Define dissemination platforms. Set up a ResearchGate project account. Set up a Zenodo project account.	Continuous uploading of EU accepted reports, AI-Mind publications and other resources to platforms. Develop the scientific community on ResearchGate.	Submit resources to the WHO’s platform. Assess resources available on dissemination platforms.

AI-Mind events	Organise first webinars. Hold internal meetings with key points broadcast to audiences.	Organise webinars and workshops in scientific conferences, including HBP and EBRAINS, relevant fairs.	Organise webinars and seminars. Organise workshops and demonstrations on AI-Mind tools.
Conferences and workshops	Present project scope and interact with participants.	Present project results and interact with participants.	Present project results and interact with participants. Showcase AI-Mind tools and present exploitation pathways.
Publications	Establish publication rules and processes within the consortium.	Regular publications from AI-Mind partners in high-impact journals and relevant outlets.	Control publications from AI-Mind regarding Open Science policy.
Engagement with stakeholders and community building	Establish contact points on national and international levels. Collect requirements from target groups.	Validate results with key stakeholders (both online and offline), interact with health, scientific and industry communities. Hold an AI-Mind session at the AE conference. Develop the AI-Mind Knowledge Hub.	Create a network of potential users of AI-Mind tools, invite to demonstrations, trainings and webinars. Hold AI-Mind session at the AE conference. Obtain regular content updates of the Knowledge Hub and collect feedback.
Collaboration with other initiatives	Identify synergies, establish contact points, first meetings and webinars (e.g. EBRAINS, HBP, BRAINTEASER).	Periodic bilateral exchange of news and results, joint presence in events.	Joint engagement in events. Create potential collaborations in future EU projects.
Contribution to scientific and technological advancements	Participate in relevant working groups. Align AI-Mind technology with EU regulations.	Develop best practices and guidelines for health professionals included in AI-Mind starter kit.	Evaluate starter kit based on feedback loop. Organise demonstrations for the use of AI-Mind tools.

Although most of the dissemination activities are meant to start in M13, AI-Mind partners have already been very active **during the first year of the project** and have presented AI-Mind at numerous conferences:

Table 6 Some of conferences where AI-Mind partners presented in the first year of the project.

Conference Title	Date	Project Partner	Audience Reached
Norwegian Smart Care Cluster – How to prevent and delay dementia	04.03.2021	Dr Ira Haraldsen (OUS)	Health professionals, the general public, people with dementia

HTAi RWE 2021 virtual Annual Business Meeting	29.06.2021	Dr Signe Daugbejrg (UCSC)	Health professionals
Second RWE-AI IG Quarterly Meeting	08.07.2021	Dr Signe Daugbejrg (UCSC)	Health professionals
Midnight sun conference for Patient-Centered Artificial Intelligence	15-16.06.2021	Dr Ira Haraldsen (OUS)	Health professionals
NO-Age and NO-AD Seminar	28.06.2021	Dr Ira Haraldsen (OUS)	The general public, the scientific community
Human Brain Project Summit 2021	12-15-10-2021	Dr Ira Haraldsen (OUS)	The scientific community, policymakers
Global AI Festival	24-11-2021	Prof. Pedro Lind	The scientific community
The Professional Society for Health Economics and Outcomes Research (ISPOR) Value in Health	02.12.2021	Dr Signe Saugbjerg (UCSC)	Scientific community
Virtual ISPOR Europe 2021	02.12.2021	Dr Signe Saugbjerg, Prof. Americo Cichetti (UCSC)	Scientific community

6.4 Sustainability

Sustainability is difficult to achieve in funded projects that have an end date. However, several activities undertaken by AI-Mind will continue to have an impact beyond the project's end:

- Relations built with cohorts and patient groups will ensure the continuation of activities aimed at raising awareness about dementia risk factors, the importance of early prediction and AI-Mind findings.
- Published scientific articles will extend AI-Mind' impact in the research community in the long term.
- The AI-Mind Knowledge Hub, with available resources, will be linked for use by different stakeholders through the project website up to five years after the end of the project.
- The AI-Mind Connector and Predictor will be further exploited with the aim of implementing them in clinical practice across Europe.
- After the end of the project, accelCH will develop a post-project website, which will continue to inform the target groups about the project's results and impact. The website will be available for at least five years after the end of the project.

In addition, exploitation activities that will be set as part of innovation management (IM) as well as a path-to-market strategy (D7.5) will contribute to ensuring the long-term sustainability of AI-Mind. Following the guidelines from the International Organisation for Standardization (ISO) published as standard [56002:2019 for the management of innovation](#), accelCH will support AI-Mind partners in developing an IM framework tailored to project's needs. This will maximise the impact of AI-Mind innovations and exploitable outcomes.

7 How will we know whether our plan is effective?

All activities aim to achieve the communication and dissemination objectives defined in the sections above. They have been planned based on the current knowledge of the target groups, the expected project progress and experience from previous projects in which AI-Mind partners were involved. Over the time span of AI-Mind, project- or target group-related factors might change. Some activities will prove effective while others will prove less effective. As the consortium is dedicated to reaching maximum impact, repeated evaluation and adjustment are necessary based **on feedback loops** per activity. This improvement cycle will take place at relevant points of time during the project or periodically, depending on the activity's evaluation method.

A tool developed and provided by accelCH, [accelCOCKPIT®](#), facilitates the management of the project by tracking all tasks, milestones, risks and deliverables throughout the AI-Mind lifecycle, including those related to communication and dissemination.

To measure the impact of planned DISCO activities and to conduct a precise evaluation of public engagement, both quantitative and qualitative indicators must be considered. In this context, measuring these indicators on a regular basis is important for understanding whether progress is being made or whether additional measures must be implemented to ensure that target values are achieved.

Joanna Plesniak
(accelCH)
Lead for dissemination
and communication

I enjoy translating complex information into engaging communication so that a broad range of audiences are reached and can benefit from scientific breakthroughs. It's rewarding to see all AI-Mind partners committed to the common goal.

Evaluation and adjustment in AI-Mind is based on the process involving either direct or indirect feedback.

7.1 Monitoring and evaluation

Success can only be measured against defined objectives. The objectives need to be specific, measurable, achievable, realistic and time-bound (SMART). The criteria measuring the achievement of these objectives are called key performance indicators (KPIs). The defined KPIs for AI-Mind measure the quantitative and qualitative aspects of DISCO activities. The quantity of engagements with the target groups is easier to measure, but only together with a measurement of quality, such as the increased awareness or attitude towards the AI-Mind project, can the effectiveness be evaluated and enhanced through according adaptations.

Online and digital channels and media often offer integrated tools to measure their impact over longer periods via website analytics or the number of followers. Here, the evaluation should not only focus on the numbers but should also take into consideration the interlinkages and/or interdependencies of the AI-Mind activities. For example, if there is an increase in the number of visitors to the website, this does not necessarily mean the website is meeting its targets; it could be linked to a new publication which increased interest and drew more visitors to the website. If the website does not meet the visitor’s expectations, the duration of their stay on the website will be short.

Figure 27 The AI-Mind website analytics – an overview of the visitors and sessions in the first reporting period. Increasing tendency in the number of visitors indicates that implemented outreach activities increase the project awareness and generate interest amid target audiences.

As shown in Figure 27, over the first year, the AI-Mind website generated 900 visitors per month on average. The increased tendency was marked after M5 due to outreach activities performed by the communication team and consortium members. These included interviews with project partners, news articles, social media campaigns, promotion of the explanatory video and participation in relevant events. From the 10 most visited pages, which cover 91% of the website traffic, [Studie Norge](#) is in the lead with more than 5,400 unique page views, followed by the [Home page](#), [Project](#), [Partners](#) and [Research and Innovation](#). Different factors influence the number of visitors and the way they engage with the AI-Mind website, including user-friendly design, available content and its optimisation towards search engines, as well as how the website is linked in other communication means. For

example, the traffic on the Norwegian study page is much higher than on other local study pages, as OUS has broadly linked it in its communication for recruitment to the AI-Mind study.

Figure 28 The AI-Mind website analytics – an overview of the number of visitors to specific pages.

An important part of the evaluation process is to allow feedback loops to reassess and adapt activities and approaches when targets are not met. As print material does not allow automatic feedback, accelCH is highly dependent on input from all partners, not only to use and distribute material but also to send feedback so that the usefulness of materials and activities can be evaluated. To monitor DISCO activities and see whether the consortium is reaching its goal of engaging the right target groups through the AI-Mind actions, all partners will continuously update the accelDISCO CONSOLE with performed activities. This information will be further analysed and assessed by the Ai-Mind communication team.

The purpose of evaluating dissemination activities is to ensure that all partners and stakeholders are aware of the results achieved in the project and that these measures are appropriate to the audience. Furthermore, although the aim is to achieve as much positive feedback as possible, negative feedback should also be taken into consideration, as it can highlight limitations that will help guide the project towards maximising its impact and facilitating future exploitation.

7.2 Assessment methods

7.2.1 Quantitative assessment

The numeric verification of the activities' impact is useful in deciding how to proceed with the implementation of the outreach plan. If, after a first evaluation, some activities do not yield the expected results, they need to be adapted. To achieve a high level of efficiency, this cycle of implementation, evaluation and adaptation is the key to best benefit from learning effects within the project. accelCH will continuously monitor the performance and the communication team will assess activities to apply corrections in due time.

Table 7 An overview of KPIs and the planned assessment of the AI-Mind DISCO activities

DISCO Mean	KPIs	Target Value	Data Source
Project website	Number of visitors Average session duration	Average of 500 visitors per month, increasing tendency	Website metrics (Google Analytics)
Twitter	Number of followers Number of tweets Number of tweet impressions Number of mentions	500 followers 20 shares/comments per tweet	Twitter account metrics
LinkedIn	Number of followers Number of posts	500 followers 80 posts, 20 likes/shares/comments per post	LinkedIn account metrics
Facebook	Number of followers Number of posts Number of impressions and engagement rate	500 followers 80 posts, 20 likes/shares/comments per post	Facebook account metrics
YouTube	Number of videos uploaded Number of views Total watch time	10 videos uploaded 50 views per video	YouTube account metrics
Press & online media	Number of published articles/news releases Audience reach	25 articles/press releases on AI-Mind published 10 features per AI-Mind press release	Published, articles collected
Website news articles	Number of news articles published / Traffic on the news page	At least 1 article per month (min. 48 in total)	News entries on the website
Video series	Number of videos developed Number of views on YouTube	10 videos produced 50 views per video	Consortium information YouTube metrics
Factsheet	Number of downloads from the website	100 downloads	Website metrics

Infographic	Number of downloads from the website	100 downloads per item	Website metrics
Dementia events	Number of events Number of participants	At least 4 events 50 people per event	Consortium information
Explanatory videos	Number of views on YouTube Number of displays per study location	200 views 100 displays	Website metrics Consortium information
Flyer	Number of flyers distributed	Distribution of 100 flyers in events or through partners' local networks	Consortium information
Poster	Use of posters and roll-ups at presentations and events	Posters/roll-up used in 15 events	Partner feedback
AE Newsletter	Number of downloads,	500 downloads per newsletter	AE website metrics
Global dementia Observatory Knowledge Exchange Platform	Number of resources accepted	At least 1 resource on GDO KE Platform	Information of acceptance from WHO
ResearchGate	Number of reads	Minimum 20 per publication	ResearchGate analytics
Open Research Data	Number of publications that use shared data	Minimum of 3 uses of shared data	Consortium information
Zenodo	Number of resources uploaded	49 public deliverables available on Zenodo	Zenodo analytics
"Dementia in Europe" special issue	Number of issues distributed	2,500 issues distributed in print and digital form	Consortium information
AI-Mind events	Number of participants and participants' feedback	Depending on the format: webinars and workshops minimum of 20 participants, AI-Mind sessions: 100 participants	Consortium information, registration forms
International conferences	Number of talks and poster presentations	30 presentations Peer feedback	Consortium information
Scientific publications	Number of publications Impact factor and h-index	30 publications in high-impact journals	Peer-reviewed journals/publications tracking list
Knowledge Hub	Number of resources Average session duration	At least 20 resources available	Website analytics
Starter kit	Number of materials distributed/downloaded	50 downloads from the website	Website analytics Consortium information

Demonstrators	Number of participants and their feedback	20 participants per clinical site	Consortium information
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7.2.2 Qualitative assessment

The consortium will actively invite stakeholders for critical feedback, encouraging both input for improvements and confirmation of well-perceived activities. The analysis and feedback results will then be compared to the set targets. Attention will be paid to the context of the feedback, such as the local culture.²⁰ While the numbers of the quantitative assessment will already serve as an indicator of whether DISCO activities have been effective, the feedback will show how the activities have been perceived. If the feedback is positive in most cases, it will indicate that the communication and dissemination activities are effective. Negative or no feedback shall be analysed and if justified and possible, the implementation of the affected activities adjusted.

7.3 Reports and adjustments of planned activities

For each of the four periodic reports, the DISCO plan will be updated with completed activities and an evaluation of the measures taken up to each point. Based on the outcome of the evaluation, the DISCO plan will be adjusted, incorporating lessons learned to optimise AI-Mind strategies for communication and dissemination. Moreover, deliverable 7.4 “Outreach reports” due in M48 of the project will provide detailed information on performed dissemination and communication activities, including their evaluation and effectiveness assessment.

All DISCO activities will be routinely monitored and documented with the input of all involved consortium members to provide a profound basis for DISCO plan updates. The activities will be specifically evaluated during the feedback periods, as indicated above, but feedback outside these periods will also be considered. Based on the evaluation, the consortium partners will adapt upcoming activities if needed to maximise the reach and relevance of all planned communication and dissemination actions.

8 What is our key take away?

The DISCO plan has been developed to provide guidance to all AI-Mind’s consortium members on making the project results available and to transform their work, achievements and research results into a mid- and long-term impact by meeting DISCO objectives.

Our partners will address their communication and dissemination activities towards the most important stakeholders, which includes health professionals, the scientific community and people with MCI and the community of people with dementia, conference audiences and key opinion leaders within the disciplines involved, as well as various media outlets to reach a wider audience. Activities include diverse direct and indirect communication acts, online and nondigital formats, with stakeholders already aware of AI-Mind and those whose interests are not yet engaged. AI-Mind Knowledge Hub and AI-Mind events are key activities that foster follow-up R&I. Diverse activities are directed at clinicians to have an active exchange with potential mediators of the early implementation of AI-Mind outcomes. In addition, publications with open access will make the results available to every interested person worldwide.

Led by accelCH, the consortium members will now implement the planned WP7 activities according to the agreed timeline. The impact of the activities will be evaluated regularly, and the DISCO plan will be adjusted based on the feedback. External and internal circumstances influencing the activities will also be incorporated. All in all, the present plan will be treated as a dynamic document, guiding the consortium members to a beneficial sharing and usage of AI-Mind’s outcomes.

Dr Jeanette Müller
(accelCH)
Innovation Manager of
the AI-Mind project

The AI-Mind project and solution have a huge innovation potential that could make a difference to many people. I am therefore honoured to guide the project partners through the innovation process and facilitate the exploitation of project results.

9 Annexes

- Annex 1: Initial stakeholders` identification
- Annex 2: Most relevant initiatives and potential collaborations
- Annex 3: Initial identification of dissemination opportunities
- Annex 4: Relevant outlets for scientific publications
- Annex 5: Communication and dissemination activities overview
- Annex 6: Implementation roadmap (GANTT)

9.1 Annex 1 – Initial stakeholders identification

Stakeholders	Sub group	Example
Clinics & hospitals	Clinics Norway	OUS
	Clinics Finland	HUH, neurology clinics in Helsinki
	Clinics Italy	IRCCS, UCSC
	Clinics Spain	UCM, Hospital Clinico San Carlos
Healthcare providers	General practitioners	GPs group Allmennlegeinitiativet
	Electrophysiologists	AI-Mind partners and their networks
	Clinical neurologists/neuropsychologists	AI-Mind clinical sites, collaborators from EBRAINS and other EU projects
	Other clinical staff (e.g. nurses)	HUH clinical nurses
Health Technology Assessment	European Network for Health Technology Assessment (EUnetHTA)	HTA working groups
	Health Technology Assessment International	Special interest group RWE-AI
Memory clinics	European/national	European Memory Clinics Association, OUS Memory Clinic, UCM Memory Clinic,

	Insurance companies		IMG, AXA, Allianz
	Patients' Associations	International associations	Alzheimer's Association International, Dementia Alliance International
		European associations	Alzheimer Europe
		National associations	Nordic permed law, Fundacion cien Madrid, ES, AFADEMA (Spain), Centro de Prevención del Deterioro Cognitivo
	Informal carers	Family members of people with dementia, Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease	Alzheimer Society of Finland, Nasjonalforeningen for folkehelsen
	People with MCI & dementia	People with cognitive decline in Norway, Spain, Italy, Finland	Alzheimer's Society, Young Dementia Network
		MEG Producers	MEGIN
	Communities	EU R& I Initiatives, including communities in neuroimaging, computer science	NORA, CLAIRE, EBRAINS
	Educational institutions	Research organisations and communities, clinical, technology organisations and universities	EBRAINS, Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI), The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Association, universities partnering in the project
	Health diagnostics equipment	Technology providers	Finnish Center for Artificial Intelligence, Cambridge Cognition, Accenture (Spain)
	AI and data management	Health technology startups/incubators	Parkinson develop ICT

	<p>Pharma companies</p>	<p>Pharmaceutical companies interested in new technologies</p>	<p>Roche, Merck, Novo nordisk</p>
	<p>Policymakers</p>	<p>European level</p>	<p>High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI HLEG), WHO, European Reference Networks (ERNs) European Centre of Excellence on the Regulation of Robotics & AI (EURA), Ministry of Health and Care Service/NOR</p>
		<p>National bodies</p>	
		<p>Local governments</p>	<p>City Council (Oslo, Rome, Madrid, Helsinki)</p>
		<p>NGOs</p>	<p>Alzheimer’s Association International, Dementia Alliance International</p>
	<p>Funding agencies</p>	<p>Funding agencies European level</p>	<p>EC, Innovative Medicine Initiative</p>
		<p>Funding agencies national level</p>	<p>NordForsk, The Carlos III Health Institute</p>
	<p>European public</p>	<p>People interested in health care, research, innovations</p>	<p>Public in the area of Oslo, Helsinki, Rome and Madrid Social network groups, family members of people with dementia</p>
	<p>Private medical centres</p>	<p>Individuals working in the care sector</p>	<p>Quirón clinics, HM Hospitales (Spain)</p>

9.2 Annex 2 – Most relevant initiatives and potential collaborations

Acronym	Project title	Website	Duration
ID-earlyMCI	Objective home-based EEG prediction of aMCI: Identification of a predictive electrophysiological model of cognitive function in amnesic mild cognitive impairment.	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/893823	Oct.2020 – Sep.2022
BRAINTEASER	BRinging Artificial INTelligence home for a better cAre of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis and multiple SclERosis	https://brainteaser.health/	Jan.2021 – Dec.2024
LETHE	LETHE (λήθη) – A personalized prediction and intervention model for early detection and reduction of risk factors causing dementia, based on AI and distributed Machine Learning	https://www.lethe-project.eu/	Jan.2021 – Dec.2024
VPH-DARE@IT	VPH Dementia Research Enabled by IT	http://vph-dare.eu/	Apr.2013 – Mar.2017
NORATEST	NORATEST: An e-Health solution for a better Alzheimer's diagnosis and management	https://www.alzohis.com/en/company	Dec.2019 – Mar.2020
EPAD	European Prevention of Alzheimer’s Dementia Consortium	https://ep-ad.org/	Jan.2015 – Dec.2019
VirtualBrainCloud	Personalized Recommendations for Neurodegenerative Disease	https://virtualbraincloud-2020.eu/	Dec.2018 – Nov.2022

MindTrack	Analysis of eye vergence responses for the early detection and monitoring of cognitive and mental disorders	http://www.braingaze.com/	Nov.2019 – Apr.2020
ElectroMAD	The Fast Periodic Visual Stimulation: a sensitive and objective approach to identify early cognitive markers of AD	https://face-categorization-lab.webnode.com/	Apr.2016 – Mar.2018
ADDIA	Validation of a fast and simple peripheral blood diagnostic biomarker kit for Alzheimer’s disease	http://www.addia-project-h2020.eu/	Aug.2015 – Jul.2019
PATHAD	Pathways to Alzheimer's disease	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/681712	Dec.2016 – Nov.2021
PANA	PROMOTING ACTIVE AGEING: FUNCTIONAL NANOSTRUCTURES FOR ALZHEIMER’S DISEASE AT ULTRA-EARLY STAGES.	https://panaproject.eu/	Mar.2016 – Aug.2021
RADAR-AD	Remote Assessment of Disease and Relapse – Alzheimer’s Disease	https://www.radar-ad.org/	Jan.2019 – Jun.2022
VERDAD	A blood based biomarker identifying early Alzheimer Disease's pathology	https://pre-diagnostics.com/	Jun.2019 – Nov.2021

9.3 Annex 3 – Initial identification of dissemination opportunities

External event	Target audience	Start date	End date
<u>Alzheimer's association international conference 2021</u>	Scientific community, Healthcare professionals	26.07.2021	30.07.2021
<u>Mediterranean seminar for consciousness</u>	Scientific community, Healthcare professionals	04.09.2021	12.09.2021
<u>Human brain project summit 2021</u>	Scientific community, Policymakers, Industry	12.10.2021	15.10.2021
<u>Nora - nordic young researchers symposium 2021</u>	Scientific community	01.11.2021	02.11.2021
<u>NordForsk The ethics of artificial intelligence in health care and research</u>	Scientific community	02.11.2021	02.11.2021
<u>Digital life Norway conference</u>	Scientific community	10.11.2021	11.11.2021
<u>Building Global Momentum for Interventions in Alzheimer's Disease Lausanne workshop viii</u>	Scientific community, Policymakers, Regulatory bodies, Patient organisations	15.11.2021	18.11.2021
<u>Nora annual conference</u>	Scientific community	17.11.2021	18.11.2021

<u>ISPOR Europe 2021</u>	Scientific community, Industry, HTA & Regulatory bodies, Policymakers	02.12.2021	02.12.2021
<u>Health Technology Assessment International HTAi 2021</u>	Scientific community, Industry, HTA & Regulatory bodies, Policymakers	29.06.2021	29.06.2021
<u>Real World Evidence and Health Technology Assessment International 2021</u>	Scientific community, Industry, HTA & Regulatory bodies, Policymakers	08.07.2021	08.07.2021
<u>31st Alzheimer Europe conference</u>	Patients organisations, General public, People with MCI and dementia, Policymakers	29.11.2021	01.12.2021
<u>Ean-ebrains joint workshop</u>	Scientific community	09.12.2021	11.12.2021
<u>AD/PD™ 2022 - The 16th International Conference on Alzheimer's & Parkinson's Diseases</u>	Scientific community, Healthcare professionals, Patients organisations, General public	15.03.2022	20.03.2022
<u>16th World Congress on Controversies in Neurology</u>	Scientific community, Healthcare professionals, Patients organisations	24.03.2022	27.03.2022
<u>35th global conference of alzheimer's disease international</u>	Healthcare professionals, Patients organisations, General public, People with MCI and dementia, Policymakers	08.06.2022	10.06.2022
<u>Nora annual conference 2022</u>	Scientific community	09.06.2022	10.06.2022
<u>HTAi 2022</u>	Scientific community, Industry, HTA & Regulatory bodies, Policymakers	25.06.2022	29.06.2022

<u>EAN Congress 2022</u>	Scientific community, Healthcare professionals, Policymakers	25.06.2022	28.06.2022
<u>7th neurological disorders summit</u>	Scientific community, Healthcare professionals, Policymakers	18.07.2022	21.07.2022
<u>EMBC 43rd Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society</u>	Scientific community, Industry	11.07.2022	15.07.2022
<u>FENS Forum 2022</u>	Scientific community, Healthcare professionals, Policymakers, General public	09.07.2022	13.07.2022
<u>Alzheimer's association international conference</u>	Patients organisations, General public, People with MCI and dementia, Policymakers	31.07.2022	04.08.2022
<u>15th clinical trials on alzheimer's disease</u>	Patients organisations, Healthcare professionals, General public, People with MCI and dementia, Policymakers	29.11.2022	02.12.2022
<u>32nd alzheimer europe conference</u>	Patients organisations, Healthcare professionals, General public, People with MCI and dementia, Policymakers	05.12.2022	07.12.2022

9.4 Annex 4 – Relevant outlets for scientific publications

Publication outlet name	Type	Target Audience	Frequency of publication
European Journal of Neuroscience (EJN)	Academic journal	Scientific community	Biweekly
Annals of Neurology	Academic journal	Scientific community	Monthly
Alzheimer’s & Dementia	Academic journal	Scientific community	Monthly
Journal of Neurology	Academic journal	Scientific community	Monthly
EU Journal of Alzheimer Disease	Academic journal	Scientific community	Monthly
BRAIN	Academic journal	Scientific community	Monthly
PloS ONE	Academic journal	Scientific community	Monthly
LancetNeurology	Academic journal	Scientific community	Monthly
Lancet Digital Health	Academic journal	Scientific community	Monthly
The Lancet Healthy Longevity	Academic journal	Scientific community	Monthly
The Lancet Regional Health – Europe	Academic journal	Scientific community	Monthly
Neurology	Academic journal & Online platform	Scientific community	Bimonthly

Artificial intelligence in medicine	Academic journal	Scientific community	Monthly
The Journal of the European College of Neuropsychopharmacology	Academic journal	Scientific community	Monthly
Alzheimer Europe: Dementia in Europe magazine	Policy magazine	Scientific community & Policy community	Every 4 months
Nature Machine Intelligence	Academic journal	General public	Monthly
Open Access Government Journal	Academic journal	General public	Quarterly
IEEE Journals	Academic journal	Scientific community	Unknown
Society & AI	Academic journal	Scientific community	Quarterly
International Journal of Human-Computer Studies	Academic journal	Scientific community	Monthly
ACM Journals	Academic journal	Scientific community	Monthly
Nature Aging	Academic journal	Scientific community	Monthly
npj Digital Medicine	Academic Journal	Scientific community	Monthly
Scientific Reports	Academic Journal	Scientific community	Monthly

9.5 Annex 5 Communication and dissemination activities overview

ID	Activity name (channel(s) and tool(s))	Implementation Project Month (M)	Main clusters of target groups						Responsibility		KPIs target value	Expected impact
			Healthcare system	Patients' advocacy	Science community	Industry	Regulatory bodies	Other (general public)	Lead	Contribution		
Communication activities about the project												
1	Website	M1-M60	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	accelCH	All partners	approx. 500 visitors/month	Raised awareness about AI-Mind, MCI and dementia
2	Social media (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube)	M1-M60	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	accelCHOUS	All partners	500 followers per account, 20 shares / comments per post, 80 posts per account, 50 video views	Raised awareness of AI-Mind and project activities
3	Digital publishing (press releases, news items/articles, digital stories)	M1-M60	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	accelCH	All partners	48 articles/press releases average 10 features/press release	Raised awareness of AI-Mind and project activities
4	Digital Newsletters	M1-M60	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	accelCH	All partners	500 downloads/newsletter	Raised awareness of AI-Mind and project activities

5	Video series	M10-M48	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	accelCH	All partners	10 videos developed	Knowledge sharing and raising awareness, supporting recruitment to the AI-Mind study
6	Digital and print materials (flyers, factsheets, brochures, posters)	M1-M60	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	accelCH	All partners	100 distributed per item/print; min. 100 downloads per item/digital	Raised awareness of AI-Mind and project activities
7	Dementia prevention events	M19-M48	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	OUS, HUH, UCM, IRCCS	accelCH, AE	min. 4 events, 50 people/event	Awareness raising and knowledge sharing
Communication activities about the study												
8	Local recruitment activities	M6-M16	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	OUS, HUH, UCM, IRCCS	accelCH	250 participants recruited study location	Increased recruitment and awareness of the project
9	Study materials – digital and print (study pages, explanatory video, flyer)	M6-M12	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	accelCH	OUS, HUH, UCM, IRCCS	500 visitors; 200 views; min. 100 flyers distributed/print	Awareness raising and knowledge sharing
AI-Mind and the community of people with dementia												
10	AE Newsletter	M1-M60	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	accelCH, AE	All partners	500 downloads/newsletter	Raised awareness of AI-Mind and project activities
11	AE Website	M1-M60	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	AE	All partners	approx. 500 visitors/month,	Raised awareness of AI-Mind and project activities
12	AE Social media channels	M1-M60	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	accelCH, AE	All partners	500 followers/channel, 80 posts/channel, 20 shares	Raised awareness of the AI-Mind project and increased collaboration

											/comments/likes per post/tweet	
13	Dementia in Europe magazine	M2, M55-M60	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	AE	All partners	2500 issues distributed in print and digital	Raise awareness about the AI-Mind project among different target groups
14	Alzheimer Europe Annual Conference	M31-M60	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	AE	All partners	600 participants/conference	Involved national associations in outreach activities performed by clinical partners
Dissemination of project results												
15	Global Dementia Knowledge Exchange Platform	M49-M60	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	accelCH, OUS	All partners	min. 1 resource accepted	Distribution of data for future use in scientific research, knowledge sharing and advocacy
16	Research Gate	M10-M60	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	OUS	All partners	min. 20 reads/publication	Broaden the project dissemination outreach and visibility of project results
17	Open Research data	M12-M60	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	OUS	All partners	min. 3 uses of shared data	Distribution of data for future use in scientific research, knowledge sharing and advocacy
18	Zenodo	M10-M60	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	accelCH OUS	All partners	49 public deliverables	Distribution of data for future use in scientific research, knowledge sharing and advocacy

19	“Dementia in Europe” special issue from AI-Mind	M49-M60	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	AE	All partners	2500 issues distributed in print and digital form	Disseminate the information about the AI-Mind project activities to people with MCI and general public
AI-Mind events – knowledge sharing												
22	Webinar series	M2-M60	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	OUS, DNV GL, accelCH, EBRAINS	All partners	20 participants/webinar	Provide the information about the project scope, results, and AI-Mind tools. Establish the interaction with participants.
23	AI-Mind session at Alzheimer Europe Conference	M49-M60	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	AE	All partners	600 participants	Project activities and outcomes will be delivered to people in the dementia community
24	AI-Mind at the European Parliament	M31-M48	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	AE	All partners	100 participants	Disseminate AI-Mind project results to policymakers at the EU level
25	International conferences	M1-M60	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	OUS	All partners	30 presentations	Peer scrutiny, validation of results, and knowledge sharing
26	Peer-reviewed open access publications	M13-M60	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	OUS	All partners	min. 30 high impact publications	Knowledge sharing, stimulating future research and potential collaborations
AI-Mind Knowledge Hub												
27	“Brain Collection”	M19-M48	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	OUS, AE, accelCH	All partners	min. 20 resources	Increased knowledge on dementia prevention and intervention

28	PhD & Young Researcher Club	M13-M48	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	OUS	All partners	min. 3 sessions yearly, min 10 developed resources available, min. 5 online courses listed	Establish collaborations with scientists, support early-stage researchers as well as PhD students
29	AI-Mind Educational Toolboxes	M49-M60	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	OUS	All partners	min. 10 toolboxes developed	Provide information for clinicians and healthcare providers about new diagnostics tools
AI-Mind tools – the AI-Mind Connector and Predictor												
30	AI-Mind starter kit	M10-M60	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	HUH	Clinical partners	50 downloads	Health professionals have a better understanding of screening methods and can use AI-Mind solutions.
31	Demonstrators	M49-M60	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	BrainSymph, Neuroconnect, Lurtis	Clinical partners accelCH	20 participants/ clinical site	Lowered barriers for the uptake of the AI-Mind tools and increased knowledge on the benefits of early intervention.

9.6 Annex 6 Implementation roadmap (GANTT)

A full document is available as an excel file to all AI-Mind partners on the internal platform (accelCLOUD) and as a living document will be updated in line with the project progress.

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